

D1.2 Capacity Development Strategy for DIRECTED

Training of Trainers – Implementing transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes in Real World Labs

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Report overview

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Executive summary

This report outlines the Capacity Development Strategy for training on transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes, supported and structured by the Tandem framework for co-production (Daniels et al., 2020; Bharwani et al., 2024). Knowledge co-production is an approach that aims to support the operationalization of the DIRECTED Risk-Tandem Framework. Risk-Tandem addresses several interoperability, governance and communication challenges, related to disaster risk management (DRM), climate change adaptation (CCA) and systemic risk management. The Framework will be implemented through the capacity development and Training of Trainers (ToT) of Real World Lab (RWL) hosts (WP 1¹), with an emphasis on enabling locally led knowledge co-production of data and model interoperability (WP 2), risk governance (WP 3) and the data fabric (WP 5) led by an understanding of RWL challenges and potential solutions.

The Strategy outlines the practical, iterative, and context-driven approach to capacity development, including module descriptions and a timeline for the first year, and lays the foundation for further development of learning materials, ensuring alignment with DIRECTED's overarching objectives and ambitions. The strategy ends with a description of the proposed Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL) plan, to be co-developed with RWL hosts (Trainers) and stakeholders for a comprehensive evaluation of the quality and impact of DIRECTED's co-production processes.

The Capacity Development Strategy has been informed by RWL scoping activities, continuous RWL engagement and a literature review covering the theoretical and contextual challenges of multi-hazard risk governance in the European context, as well as integrating different DRM and CCA knowledges, data, or disciplines towards holistic risk reduction. The Strategy has been delivered via online and in-person training sessions and capacity development modules, support consultations, planning workshops and complementary activities. The ultimate aim is to empower Trainers to enable locally tailored implementation of DIRECTED based on priorities identified by stakeholders themselves, reflecting the unique needs in the Capital Region of Copenhagen, Emilia-Romagna, the Danube, and the Rhine-Erft Regions, both now and beyond the lifetime of the project.

¹ See annex 1.

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List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
CCA	CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION
DMP	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
DRM	DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT
DRR	DISASTER RISK REDUCTION
MEL	MONITORING, EVALUATION AND LEARNING
RWL	REAL WORLD LAB
TOT	TRAINING OF TRAINERS
WP	WORK PACKAGE

1 Introduction

This capacity development strategy explains the operationalization of the Tandem process for co-production within RWLs (as a part of the Risk-Tandem Framework), focusing creating an enabling environment for collaboration, and the design of co-produced holistic risk management approaches. It combines SEI's Tandem approach to co-production (Daniels, et al., 2019; 2020; Bharwani et al., 2024) with capacities required for its implementation, keeping in mind the various tools, approaches, and methods developed for holistic risk governance and data interoperability under **Work Packages** (WP) 3 and 5 as a part of the DIRECTED process. In detail, the strategy will:

1. Explain the rationale and capacities required for knowledge co-production in risk governance context, and the approach to cultivating enabling environments through the Tandem process.
2. Set the approach for identifying capacity needs together with **Real World Labs** (RWLs) to support the integration of CCA and DRM, and systemic risk management via knowledge co-production (in alignment with the Tandem process).
3. Build the foundation for empowering stakeholders, scientists, and modellers alike to develop their capacity and skills in enabling and institutionalising knowledge co-production and collaboration for risk governance to enable the exploration of their respective risk context, needs of stakeholders, and integrating data and tools into decision-making.

Most importantly, this strategy underscores knowledge-based practice, referring to the needs of professionals in risk governance. The strategy is mainly developed by **WP 4** in the DIRECTED Project, to complement WP 3 working on developing and applying the innovative and integrated risk governance framework for DRM and CCA – Risk-Tandem. The iterative application of transdisciplinary co-production processes as part of the framework are facilitated by WP 4 in the DIRECTED Real World Labs (WP 1). The capacity development strategy describes a central building block of the project's methodology and builds connections between all the Work Packages in DIRECTED (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Overview of Work Packages in DIRECTED.

To deliver the **Training of Trainers (ToT)** this document offers insight into the theoretical background of co-production and the Tandem framework and its practical applications, and outlines capacities required for its implementation. Furthermore, it provides guidance on how to tangibly implement this as a part of the wider Risk-Tandem process in the RWLs, and includes a chapter on **Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL)**. Importantly, this strategy is evolving, developed iteratively through continuous insights from RWLs. Thus, it should be approached as a guideline instead of a prescriptive manual. It will be complemented by learning materials and **e-Learning modules** to tangibly operationalize capacity development for training of trainers.

Knowledge co-production Trainer skills (including facilitation, co-design and co-creation skills) are central to this strategy. Based on SEI's Tandem framework (Bharwani, et al., 2024), this refers to an iterative process in which decision-makers, information providers, practitioners and citizens are brought together to improve the relevance, usability and legitimacy of risk information and its use in decision-making.

The contents of this strategy are structured as follows:

- A brief introduction to the background and context of DIRECTED, and how this links to knowledge co-production and capacity development
- Rationale for the approach, the principles of co-production (including associated capacities), and the Tandem framework.

- An exploration of the intended timeline over the project's four-year span, including a deep dive into the primary components of the knowledge co-production approach and elucidating tools and learning objectives, including the motivation behind the efforts of Work Packages 3 (governance) and 4 (co-production).

Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL) plays a pivotal role in efforts to inform the knowledge co-production process based on emerging evidence, and to modify its implementation depending on emerging needs (section 5). This will also contribute to addressing gaps in literature, often highlighting the lack of empirical evidence regarding the practical implementation of co-production in real-world contexts. MEL targeting the barriers and enablers to transdisciplinary collaboration will also support in identifying windows of opportunities for other work packages and lay the foundations for understanding best practices from the RWLs, exploring options for the scale-up of DIRECTED approaches (contributing to wider impact monitoring).

The MEL for knowledge co-production will be linked to DIRECTED's Theory of Change as its foundation, with two interlinked dimensions:

- In the first dimension, indicators and measures based on a mixed method contribution analysis will be developed to assess the impacts of capacity development activities to RWL hosts' ability to apply and enable knowledge co-production in their contexts.
- Assessing the quality of knowledge co-production processes in risk governance contexts, i.e., how RWLs have designed, implemented, and sustained innovative risk management throughout DIRECTED's tenure (outcome and impact monitoring for RWLs will be conducted separately under Task 1.3). Indicators for this process remain dependent on RWL stakeholders' priorities and must be co-explored and discussed jointly over time.

The following section outline the proposed timeline, followed by rationale for knowledge co-production and associated capacity development under DIRECTED, by exploring challenges of European risk landscapes and risk governance contexts in detail. Sections 2.1 and 2.2. will evidence the need and benefits of knowledge co-production for managing complex and systemic risks in a polycentric governance setting. Section 2.3. will then briefly outline the Tandem framework, and how it will support structuring knowledge co-production processes as a part of the Risk-Tandem concept. This will act as a reference for capacity development as discussed under Sections 3, 4 and 5 (MEL for co-production).

1.2 Proposed timeline and implementation

Implementation of the Tandem framework and associated capacity development for knowledge co-production is led by WP 4, and is implemented and evaluated in RWLs (WP 1).

Based on the phases of Tandem (and Risk-Tandem) in enabling a knowledge co-production process, DIRECTED has been divided into four distinct phases (Figure 2), derived from the Tandem framework (Figure 6) beginning with the Phase 1 (**Foundation** year). During this stage, RWLs will be up and established (from stakeholder engagement and analysis to setting priorities for action), and used to inform the iterative development of the WP 4 approach to enabling knowledge co-production in multi-hazard risk governance contexts.

This is followed by Phase 2 (**Growth**), which includes the continued implementation, facilitation, monitoring and evaluation of the co-production processes through ToT in alignment with the Risk-Tandem Framework. Capacity needs assessments and consultations will be a part of this process, in efforts to identify and respond to emerging capacity development needs throughout the project. Phases 3 (**Learn**) and 4 (**Sustain**) are interconnected, building upon the results of co-exploration and MEL to identify working solutions to complex risk problems, and supporting the institutionalization of DIRECTED risk governance and co-production approaches where appropriate. The final phase will also seek to facilitate lasting knowledge exchange toward wider impact, including via the dissemination of the capacity development modules for Risk-Tandem and knowledge co-production (see D6.3).

Figure 2: Proposed DIRECTED timeline for Risk-Tandem and knowledge co-production.

The implementation is entirely locally led, enabled via the Training of Trainers for (and engagement with) RWL hosts who lead labs of DIRECTED (annex 1). They will be trained on applying knowledge co-production in their risk governance contexts, and – when necessary – train their RWL stakeholders on addressing contextual challenges. The primary beneficiaries of capacity development outlined in the strategy are from the following organisations:

- Two persons from the Capital Region of Denmark hosted by Region Hovedstaden with technical support from the Technical University of Denmark.
- Three persons from Emilia-Romagna Region hosted by Civil Protection of the Emilia-Romagna Region (ARSTPC-ER) together with the ARP AE Hydrometeo Service Civil Protection Functional Centre with technical support from GecoSystema.
- Three persons from The Danube region is led by Genillard & Co. a consulting company and reinsurance broker (based in Munich) with technical support from Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research. This RWL has a sub-region in the Zala County Hungary, led by Zala Special Rescue Team, a first responder organisation of civilian volunteers.
- Two persons from The Rhine-Erft region in the federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia, covering districts of Euskirchen and Rhine-Erft, Germany, led by the Erftverband (water board).

For phase 1 (Foundation), capacity development will emphasise the enabling of co-production through building of partnerships, mapping of stakeholders, and early scoping of risk issues alongside emerging needs (T4.2). In more detail, modules of this phase seek to support the RWL Hosts capacities to build transdisciplinary labs, create opportunities for collaboration, and implement the Tandem process for knowledge co-production in complex risk contexts (as a part of the Risk-Tandem).

Beginning with a rapid capacity needs assessment (annex 3) and continuous consultations scheduled throughout 2023, the timeline provides structure for the implementation, but still remains flexible and open to emerging needs in efforts to maximize the relevance of training to RWL contexts. To ensure that the knowledge co-production process remains on track, it is necessary that various work packages, throughout the proposed timeline, actively seek input from the RWLs using the recommended tools in this strategy, such as questionnaires, Miro boards, meetings, and the like.

2 Rationale

Taking inspiration from sustainability sciences (see Miller and Wyborn, 2020), this strategy introduces a training approach for integrating knowledge co-production in risk governance contexts. This will be done as a response to theoretical and practical risk, data interoperability, and governance challenges, detailed briefly here.

i. Risks are increasingly complex and interconnected. On one hand, global supply chains and the mushrooming of shared digital and physical infrastructures continue to generate vulnerabilities and systemic issues embedded within the world system (UNDRR, 2022; Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic, the triple-disaster of Fukushima Daichi in 2011 or the eruption of the Eyjafjallajökull in 2010, all demonstrate the destructive potential of ripple effects of hazards as triggers of vulnerabilities across systems. On the other, risks are being reshaped by the relationships between climate change and socio-ecological systems, constituting numerous complex feedback loops that affect exposure and vulnerability. Consequently, there is a need to begin thinking beyond single hazards and nations, in efforts to understand how ‘global’ hazards may manifest as local disruptions when events travel across shared dependencies and geographies (Pescaroli, et al., 2018; Boin, 2018).

ii. Risks involve socio-economic dimensions. Instead of addressing risks as external threats, it is useful to emphasize how persisting economic stratification, poverty, inequality, and marginalization exacerbate and indeed create disaster risks (Blaikie, et al., 2004; Bankoff and Hilhorst, 2022; Oliver-Smith and Hoffman 2020; Lewis and Kelman, 2012). Yet, historical injustices and chronic structural conditions underpinning vulnerabilities continue to be neglected by risk management interventions, despite their centrality in sustainably addressing and mitigating disaster and climate risk impacts (IPCC, 2023; UNDRR, 2022; Wisner, 2020; Oliver-Smith and Hoffman, 2020; Sillmann, 2022). The key to managing risks (and climate change adaptation) from a holistic perspective is tied to vulnerability reduction (UNDRR, 2022). Yet, perspectives of engineering and natural sciences have often dominated disaster management efforts over ‘soft’ solutions, affecting long-term vulnerability reduction and social change (Weichselgartner, 2001). Similarly, those affected by decision-making tend to be excluded from top-down and expert-led risk governance processes (Gaillard, 2010; Gaillard and Mercer, 2013; Berkes, 2017), even though their perspectives are critical for achieving equal outcomes in risk governance and risk reduction.

iii. Risk governance involves many actors, and their actions are often siloed. Facing an unprecedented acceleration of interconnected, cascading, and transboundary risks that exceed the ability of top-down and expert-led managerial solutions to address them (Cosens, et al., 2021; Anisimov et al., 2023), the scope of and expertise involved in risk governance interventions appears to be expanding. Yet, findings of the ESPRESSO Project suggested that within countries, stakeholders may struggle in integrating science into policy or DRR and CCA practice, and strategic coordination between actors at national and local levels is rare due to lack of shared vision (Albris, et al., 2020; Booth, et al., 2020). Actors in Europe tend to operate

in silos: DRM is delivered by civil defense and disaster management authorities, CCA by environmental authorities, NGOs are often not included in formal risk management, and so on (Booth, et al., 2020). These issues are magnified at the regional level. Indeed, despite the European Union's strategic emphasis on regional integration, translating this agenda to practice in risk management has been limited. As a result, isolated national thinking, lack of willingness to foster transboundary cooperation, sectoral gaps, and clash of DRM/CCA cultures or ways of working limit the effectiveness or holistic risk management in Europe (Booth, et al., 2020; Albris, et al., 2020).

iv. Knowledge fragmentation and issues of interoperability. The issues of European risk governance are not limited to the complexity of challenges and the increasing number of actors taking part in these activities. Indeed, it is also facing a flood of information, competing knowledge systems, databases, and terminologies that are used in different ways across different disciplines. Despite their shared interests, actors involved often continue to describe risk issues from their context- or disciplinary-specific viewpoints and in distinct ways, often talking past each other due to the absence of shared meaning (Weichselgartner and Pigeon, 2015). Renn, et al., (2011:233) describe this as ambiguity generated by the 'plurality of legitimate viewpoints. Correspondingly, there is a need to begin integrating knowledges and terminologies between sectors, disciplines, and nations, and to advance coherence, for instance via the use of shared taxonomies (Booth, et al., 2020; Weichselgartner and Pigeon, 2015; Barrott et al., 2020). At the same time, solutions must be found to address the issues of data usability: without the ability to effectively navigate (and visualize, and use) information, critical knowledge about risks and projected impacts of climate change may become overlooked.

v. Limited usability and accessibility of knowledge. Discrepancies between producers and users of information contribute to barriers encountered in translating disaster and climate sciences into policy and action (Klein and Juhola, 2014; Sillmann, et al., 2022; Deubelli and Mechler, 2021; Spiekermann, et al., 2015; Fazey, et al., 2020). In climate services, such limitations have been described as the 'usability gap' (Lemos, et al., 2014), explaining how climate information may go unused if it does not meet the need of end users. In systemic risk management Sillmann, et al. (2022: 20) discuss the 'data-policy gap', following the limited integration of available risk information into policy making. On the other hand, scientific information may lose traction due to limited translation which occurs when researchers simply assume that their findings are linearly diffused into policy and practice without further effort to contextualize their findings in society (Figure 3). One must therefore move toward decision-makers and citizens as users of information to support the tailoring of information and information systems to contextual needs.

Figure 3: Pitfalls (red) and propositions (green) for maximizing the potential of DRR research in policy and practice (Spiekermann, et al., 2015).

2.1 The RWL context

Theoretical challenges as detailed above must be contextualized in the RWLs, in efforts to tie this strategy to real-world problems that can be addressed via knowledge co-production and risk governance mechanisms. To bridge this, we've summarized insights from deliverable D1.1. RWL Description and Set-up with a focus on challenges i-v as described above. This sets the stage for capacity development to address needs for knowledge integration, promoting inclusive risk governance, ensuring data compatibility, and managing multiple hazards, drawing from theoretical insights where applicable. Importantly, needs and priorities are also likely to emerge and shift during the implementation of the knowledge co-production process, due to which the RWL hosts will be engaged throughout the project to identify opportunities for tailored support later (including via capacity needs assessments).

Capital Region of Denmark (RWL 1)

RWL 1 is led by a regional public institution, the Capital Region of Denmark (RegionH), together with the Technical University of Denmark (DTU). Their primary areas of interest focus on the catchment of the Vaerebro River and Roskilde Fjord, selected due to their exposure to regular riverine and coastal flooding, respectively. These areas are also identified as high-risk areas for flood damage an issue worsened by climate change leading to erratic rainfall and cloudbursts that may instigate overflows of rivers and compromise sewer infrastructure. Drought has also been identified as a relevant hazard, as demonstrated by the 2018 heatwaves.

Numerous emergency management, DRM and CCA agencies from several municipalities operate in these areas, thus rendering risk governance a complicated task (as is often the case with polycentric governance operations). In general, the primary responsibility over hazard and risk governance lies with municipalities and their emergency management agencies, often complemented by policies enacted by national emergency management and other governmental authorities. In principle, the administrative regions have no role in terms of facilitation, coordination, and financing, though on occasion they may play a role through regional development projects.

Actors operating in this sphere face numerous challenges. For instance, very few are experienced in managing drought-related risks. Stakeholders of the first RWL 1 workshop also highlighted how municipalities and emergency management agencies require more funding and efforts to conduct joint preparedness drills, and how lack of knowledge regarding high-risk areas in cities hinder prioritisation. Improved public communication, awareness and strengthened alignment of data systems between municipalities were also highlighted, in efforts to nurture the integration of CCA and DRM practice. In terms of internal RWL capacities, the need to support stakeholder engagement has been outlined as an on-going gap, particularly in terms of identifying which actors to involve. As a response, this strategy outlines capacity development seeking to strengthen the RWLs skills increase the scope of their stakeholder engagement to support co-production and inclusive risk governance. Another issue outlined the difficulty of translating complex project ambitions and balancing them with contextual needs. Thus, this strategy will premise the development of materials to aid in on-going translation of work between stakeholders to mitigate top-down nature of programming by aligning DIRECTED with stakeholder's perceptions and priorities.

Emilia-Romagna Region (RWL 2)

RWL 2 in Emilia-Romagna is led by the Agency for Civil Protection of the Emilia-Romagna Region (ARSTPC-ER) together with the ARP AE Hydrometeorological Service Civil Protection Centre (responsible over DRR, CCA and DRM planning). The selected regions for the work of RWL 2 focus on the Rimini coastline, highly exposed to marine incursions and windstorms (including the municipalities of Bellaria-Igea, Rimini, Riccione, Misano Adriatico and Cattolica), alongside two municipalities of the Ferrara Province with high wildfire risks (Comacchio and

Mesola). As such, this RWL presents complex multi-hazard challenges for DIRECTED and stakeholders from Emilia-Romagna. Further, demonstrated by the major floods of May 2023 – involving a complex interplay of preceding droughts, severe rainfall, associated landslides and a storm at the Adriatic Sea preventing rivers from draining – the need for holistic approaches becomes evident.

Whilst ARSTPC-ER and ARPAE Hydrometeorological Service Civil Protection Functional Centre maintain authority over CCA and DRR, already identified challenges include limited coordination between various first responders, public bodies, service managers and volunteers during emergencies, as well as complexities originating from large amounts of data gathered by a vast monitoring network. Thus, the RWL hosts have expressed the need to strengthen cooperation, communication, and knowledge integration (latter pertaining to integrating data on climate change and natural hazards in particular). Lack of capacity development and cultural awareness regarding climate change in general was also discussed as a critical barrier hindering the implementation of integrated DRR and CCA. As such, this strategy comprises a proposal to strengthen capacity of Hosts (and stakeholders) to support the development of platforms and tools for data integration (and by extension, the Data Fabric) when needed, as well co-created modules seeking to facilitate stakeholder engagement toward improved coordination. Challenges also include citizen engagement and public risk communication, particularly in the case of wildfires.

In terms of internal programmatic challenges, stakeholder engagement was also highlighted as a difficulty due to the high number of organizations involved (leading to inability to involve firefighters and some initially targeted Prefectures). As a response, it is hoped that by co-creating materials on stakeholder engagement WPs 3 and 4 can support and thus jointly address these issues with RWL 2 over the early stages of DIRECTED.

The Danube Region (RWL 3)

RWL 3 is led by Genillard and Co, a consulting company and reinsurance broker known for their role in developing and implementing risk management strategies for the insurance market. They work together with the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research and the Mathias Corvinus Collegium of Hungary in efforts to support their RWL (which is further subdivided into three labs to provide a model transboundary risk governance in the Danube region). The two sub-labs are in Vienna, Austria, and Zala County of Hungary. As such, they represent immense geographical diversity and differing governance systems, both requiring a tailored approach to fully understand hazard and climate related challenges, transboundary governance issues, and their potential for co-produced solution making towards resilience.

To begin with the City of Vienna, its location at the banks of the Danube contributes to exposure to floods following rapid snow melt and heavy rainfall, particularly in spring and early summer. It is also vulnerable to droughts as the region regularly undergoes periods of reduced precipitation. Both hazards are governed by a diverse network of public authorities, private institutions, and public organizations across the levels of governance, often under the mandates of the Government of Vienna responsible for developing and implementing protection policies and projects. Environmental agencies and water management authorities

collaborate closely, and at the national level, numerous ministries convene on multi-stakeholder protection plans.

In Zala County (Southwestern Hungary) is mostly characterized by hillsides and low mountains. However, its edges also border the Lake Balaton – which bears significant influence over the local climate – and is traversed by the Zala River, tributary of the Danube. Hazards affecting the county include flooding, storms, drought and wildfires, all necessitating multi-risk thinking and habitual coordination and collaboration amidst a network of actors at different levels of governance, especially in terms of implementing the County Council's climate strategy.

Considering the diversity of these two sub-RWLs, the Danube thus represents unique challenges for risk management. Not only do they act as a model for assessing transboundary risk governance in the region, but also introduce their context-specific challenges to DIRECTED requiring tailored support. When combined with the effects of climate change (likely to exacerbate flooding, and high temperatures with various impacts on agriculture, wildfire risks, water supplies and public health), intense cross-boundary cooperation is required to strengthen climate adaptive, multi-risk management in the target areas.

Localized risk assessments, visualised information, long-term cooperation, and partnerships for flood risk management have already been expressed as potential focus areas by the stakeholders of the Danube RWLs. Internally, the hosts of RWL 3 have identified communication challenges arising from language differences, but also highlighted difficulties in reaching out to stakeholders in culturally diverse contexts with differing risk perceptions. Thus, the strategy and associated training for trainers seeks to build on these, in efforts to support tailored stakeholder engagement with respect to the needs of each country/stakeholder needs.

Rhine-Erft Region (RWL 4)

RWL 4 is in the federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany. Currently, it comprises the districts of Euskirchen and Rhine-Erft, which together include 21 municipalities. It is an area exposed to flooding – particularly in areas belonging to the North German Lowlands – altered by legacies of agriculture and open-pit lignite mining. Thus, and alongside relatively high flood risks, the hydrology of the region will continue to shift; particularly following the planned termination of lignite mining activities that will reduce groundwater extraction (from the current 509 million cubic meters per year). To add to these burdens, fluctuations in rainfall and temperatures (often exacerbating natural hazard impacts) have been recorded in association with climate change, thus necessitating improved communication and coordination of DRM and CCA processes across scales. Most importantly, linking municipal-level data management systems and information streams to national level structures has been outlined as a priority, alongside harmonizing existing data systems across different actors to support the flows of information pertaining to hydrometeorological hazards. Consequently, modules and training involving data, coordination and communication will be integrated into the training program, in continuous consultation with RWLs and WP 5.

In terms of risk governance, responsibilities have been spread across numerous agencies. Within the federal system, civil protection agencies maintain responsibility over water-related

hazards, whereas the district within each county maintain responsibility over disaster management. Municipalities coordinate and organize response, and some intermunicipal flood protection and private sector corporations are also involved in the RWL 4. Internally, support for broadening the scope of stakeholder engagement has been expressed by the hosts of the RWL, and thus the ambitions as outlined in this strategy are geared towards providing support for this process during the early stages of DIRECTED.

2.2 Knowledge co-production and risk governance

The previous section has identified several challenges, relating to the complexity and uncertainty of interconnected risks, issues affecting risks governance in a polycentric setting, and issues of competing knowledges involved in their management. As a response these, DIRECTED advances a perspective founded upon knowledge co-production via the Tandem framework (Daniels et al., 2020; Bharwani et al., 2024), which provides guided steps for its structured implementation (in alignment with the Risk-Tandem approach). Knowledge co-production under DIRECTED will follow the definition provided by Norström, et al. (2020), as an iterative and collaborative process involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge, and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways towards a sustainable future. For the purposes of DIRECTED, this will be revised and contextualized for the purposes risk governance (Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., 2024), towards a disaster resilient and climate adaptive future.

In in practice, knowledge co-production methods can be leveraged to generate in-depth information between local actors, modelers and scientists, as well as citizens, in efforts to understand how complex dynamics of hazards and climate change link to and interact with local conditions. Recognizing the shortfalls of siloed sciences that do not necessarily engage with real world problems (Norström, et al., 2020) that lead to gaps between science, policy, and practice (Spiekermann, et al., 2015), co-production will be introduced as a bridge. However, it is also noteworthy that complex risk challenges require innovation and solutions with transformative potential. Therefore, its potential must be discussed in more detail.

Knowledge co-production can shift perspectives from managerial perspectives toward incorporating considerations for the socio-economic and ecological contexts, in efforts to identify potential for transformative solutions and incremental changes toward lasting impact in governance approaches (Cosens, et al., 2021). For instance, by involving non-traditional perspectives and approaches to explore structural conditions and dynamics of power underpinning risk issues, co-production under DIRECTED seeks to bring forward a holistic perspective that is often neglected by technocratic risk management interventions (Issues discussed by Oliver-Smith and Hoffman, 2020; Sillmann, 2022). This also includes aspect of law, power, and accountability, all needed when identifying possible solutions for governing complexity (Cosens, et al., 2021).

It is expected that such collaboration can generate instrumental value for risk assessments and governance planning, but also **provide added benefits for the purposes of deepened collaboration between sectors, scales of governance, and disciplines**. This is required to address silos between actors, and to deepen their collaboration – challenges outlined in section 2. After all, collaboration, knowledge co-production, knowledge sharing, and shared action do not naturally emerge from shared circumstances; rather they require the building of trust, addressing of tensions, and sustained relationships (Daniels, et al., 2020; Norström, et al., 2020). Discussions regarding risk in the Real World Labs will provide a “hooking point” referring to a tangible starting point for the process (as suggested by Norström, et al., 2020).

Finally, **knowledge co-production is introduced to respond to issues of interoperability and data usability**. Co-production has introduced as a bridge between end users and data providers to support the translation of technical information for the purposes of policy and planning, and to inform modeling efforts with user needs (Daniels, et al., 2020).

However, and although the application of knowledge co-production in risk governance contexts holds immense potential for novel innovation, it should not be considered as a silver bullet. Limitations identified in academic literature include the lack of practical methods or skills required for knowledge co-production; lack of a shared definition for the term that underpins methodological confusion (Bandola-Gill, et al., 2022); lack of methods monitoring, evaluation and learning, and evidence regarding tangible outcomes (Miller and Wyborn, 2020). To address these limitations and gaps (and to contribute to further research on knowledge co-production in risk governance context), WP 4 approach in DIRECTED will build on the Tandem framework for co-production, operationalized within the Risk-Tandem process (WP 3).

3 Tandem Framework

To structure and guide capacity development on knowledge co-production processes, the Tandem framework will be introduced as the core component of the Risk-Tandem approach. The Tandem framework was initially developed to address the disconnect between research policy and adaptation action (Klein and Juhola, 2014), with a particular focus on enabling collaboration for the purposes of co-designing and co-developing adaptation solutions for climate change adaptation and sustainability challenges. Its initial commitment sought to “refocus climate services lens” (Daniels, et al., 2020), and move from products toward process-oriented engagement in which users and providers of climate information increase the ‘usability’ and impact of available climate information in planning and policy. There are also co-benefits: continued engagement is likely to generate intangible outputs – including confidence, trust, communication and increased capacity – which are required to support planning and implementation of adaptation actions (ibid.; Bharwani et al., 2024).

Figure 4: Original Tandem framework.

The framework provides iterative steps, guiding questions and advice to integrating knowledge co-production into existing planning processes. The guiding questions were developed to identify elements and characteristics of transdisciplinary co-production and stakeholder engagement supporting positive change. Further, they were designed to aid in the process of creating shared understanding, based on practical case studies (Daniels, et al., 2020). Most recently, the framework was further refined based on case studies in

Indonesia, Sweden, and Colombia to support: 1) moving from ‘useful’ to ‘usable’ information by building trust; 2) increasing institutional embedding through strengthened relationships and networks; 3) improving climate information uptake and use; 4) increasing capacity, confidence and a shared understanding of climate information by users, and the decision context by providers; and, 5) serving as a non-prescriptive guide for users, intermediaries and providers to co-design and structure an effective process for collaborative learning and action (Bharwani, et al., 2024).

The most recent iteration of the framework (Figure 5) was also refined to 1) scope and review climate and non-climate vulnerability and risks; 2) incorporate gender, social equity and power considerations; 3) acknowledge the value of local and traditional ecological knowledge; 4) co-explore horizontal and vertical governance at appropriate decision-making scales; and, 5) provide flexible starting points, with early identification of impact indicators (Bharwani et al., 2024). Due to their relevance to DIRECTED, these elements will be introduced and mainstreamed throughout capacity development and RWL activities, and its components form the foundation for the Training of Trainers for the Labs’ hosts. Building upon the associated guiding questions (see Annex 2) and practical material (by mainstreaming and combining these with risk governance processes and approaches), it seeks to enable locally led knowledge co-production in RWL settings, whilst considering multi-hazard contexts and complex risks. This approach is applied iteratively over four years (divided into distinct stages) following the Tandem elements, within the Risk-Tandem process.

Figure 5: Updated Tandem framework (Bharwani et al., 2024), emphasizing the iterative and non-linear process. The stages in the original framework, and the associated guiding questions are now captured in the nested circles (simplified for practical guidance).

It is important to note that elements in Figure 4 and 5 are not linear. Instead, each element can be revisited and revised depending on the emerging needs, context and iterative learning. The elements are support different stages of the adaptation cycle (forming the core of the Risk-Tandem Framework):

Scope, review, identify and engage. This initial phase lays the foundation for deeper discussions of challenges, goals, governance and information needs in Element 2. It seeks to inform the scoping of climate and non-climate risks, vulnerabilities and impacts, as well as support identifying and engaging relevant stakeholders from a transdisciplinary perspective (including those voices often excluded from planning and governance). This element also helps to identify and engage relevant actors and champions and can begin to nurture new collaborations and partnerships that sustain beyond the lifetime of the project. (Bharwani, et al., 2024). The guidelines will help in the holistic mapping of risks through creative and co-productive engagement methods, and outline potentially relevant actors across disciplines and the scales of governance. Under Risk-Tandem, this guidance will be combined with tools and approaches from risk governance, primarily the IRGC framework.

Co-explore. This is an opportunity to delve deeper into some of the same questions with the targeted group of stakeholders that has been identified in the first phase. It seeks to continue partnership development for successful co-production, with a focus on identifying specific risk governance challenges affecting risk management and adaptation, information needed to further understand the challenges, and to cultivate an overview of the governance landscape that affects potential solutions or management options. The different types, scales and levels of participation, engagement and knowledge in decision-making is considered when co-designing co-production activities as well as information needs, data, models, sources, assumptions, and formats (Bharwani, et al., 2024). Guidance includes questions tailored to support the co-exploration from a holistic perspective, including considerations for vulnerabilities, user-focused information needs, and the decision-making (challenges of which may become overlooked within otherwise technocratic or modelling-focused approaches). This phase also encourages the early co-design of context-led MEL indicators. The cross-cutting element of capacity development identifies how a culture of learning can be facilitated, and how this can be anchored into the implementation context through tangible outputs whilst many capacity development benefits are often intangible or difficult to measure. Discussions targeting indicators, and stakeholder feedback or reflections can be used to support this (MEL methodology further described in section 5).

Co-design will closely follow, with an emphasis of communication between stakeholders to support that developed solutions are mutually shared (and that the issues are understood, even across disciplines and scales of governance). Beginning from co-identification, the guidance will support the outlining of potential options and their appraisal, followed by notes and advice on co-design. Appraisal includes consideration of uncertainty, maladaptation, compound and cascading risks, synergies, trade-offs, and co-benefits. (Bharwani, et al., 2024). Within Risk-Tandem, co-production and co-design of solutions will build on the use of creative and engaging methods to support innovation, and the identification of windows of opportunity with transformational potential. Risk-Layering and other approaches will be used in appraising solutions, and to support prioritization (full description regarding the links between Tandem and Risk-Tandem can be found in section 5).

Integrating new knowledge and partners. This step aims at co-developing the capacities of information and service providers and their users, in efforts to integrate co-produced knowledge and solutions, and to solidify partnerships between them toward lasting collaboration (Bharwani, et al., 2024). Emphasis is placed on continued monitoring, evaluating, and learning of the process and lessons learned so far, to identify windows of opportunity for mainstreaming the work throughout existing processes with regular and systematic feedback mechanisms. Within Risk-Tandem, these will be linked to wider risk governance assessments, policy analysis and other evidence examining the RWL contexts, to identify where further support is needed to maintain and enhance the legacy and sustainability of DIRECTED.

Enhancing legacy and sustainability. This ongoing objective and ambition aims at institutionalizing knowledge co-production processes in existing governance structures (with cross-cutting emphasis on funding, communication, partnership and **capacity development**) to support the ownership, legacy and sustainability of resilient development beyond the lifetime of the project (Bharwani, et al., 2024). Before solutions can be identified, it is likely that knowledge integration, up-skilling or in-depth understanding of the co-production principles are required to produce solutions beneficial for all. The specificity of this capacity development is dependent on the contextual needs and emerging priorities as decided by stakeholders. Within Risk-Tandem, this phase will emphasize knowledge sharing and transfer, up-scaling of proposed solutions, and exploring options for maintaining strengthened risk governance processes and tools developed during the project (such as platforms for communication, or the Data Fabric). Considering the framework's roots in climate services (Daniels, et al., 2020), Tandem also supports DIRECTED's ambitions regarding improved data interoperability (WP 5). If applied strategically, knowledge co-production can aid in tailoring available information and data to user needs, with a focus on understanding the decision contexts in which information is used. Lessons from the WISER project also demonstrate how data/information products should be decision-driven and process-based, encouraging the integration of knowledge into action via shared understanding and new perspectives (Carter, et al., 2019). Under DIRECTED, these practices will be applied to support and inform the development of the Data Fabric (WP 5).

As per the Tandem framework, knowledge co-production will support non-structured exchanges, dialogic problem-solving, improvisation and adaptive governance (Slater and Robinson, 2020), all of which are required to respond to complex risks in the European context. More centrally, it may also broaden the scope of 'governance' by fostering long-term transdisciplinary collaboration and informal relationships beyond isolated disciplines. Since risk governance has been criticized for its top-down and expert-led nature that tends to disenfranchise local authorities, citizens, and communities (Wisner, 2020; Gaillard, 2010), knowledge co-production can support expanding the scope of stakeholders beyond experts and authorities at the national levels. In other words, it can break the boundaries between the governing and the governed (Berkes, 2017) to support the democratization of risk governance. Co-production is also useful to support informal collaboration, referring to the creation of spontaneous regimes that organize themselves around common purposes (Schiff, 2017). During crises, informal mechanisms often mobilize faster, and can advance more intense coordination within existing institutional mechanisms and formal arrangements due to their closer networks (Booth, et al., 2020). Most importantly, this perspective also allows the

recognition of credibility of knowledges and lived experiences of persons working at the grass-root levels, thus enabling their integration to more traditional and hierarchical notions of expertise that may fail to address local problems (Durose, et al., 2017).

Yet, **co-production isn't without its challenges**, and its application remains inconsistent, often without reference to skills or specific methods for its implementation (Miller and Wyborn, 2020). The idea has also been criticized due to its aspirational nature that tends to neglect socio-political dimensions underpinning the process – even when they may fail to facilitate change (Turnhout, et al., 2020). The issue is widely linked to the issue of monitoring and evaluating co-production; in 2015, a review revealed that 80% of the studied co-production literature did not discuss outcomes at all (Voorberg, et al., 2015) Therefore, this document will outline key capacities required to enable locally led knowledge co-production in risk governance contexts, and outline an approach to co-designed MEL.

4 Capacity development

Knowledge co-production does not simply “happen”. Rather, it requires certain capacities, opportune preconditions, and ways of working that support sustained collaboration beyond the status quo (Norström, et al., 2020). Given that contemporary risk and sustainability challenges necessitate innovation, transformations, institutionalizing of learning processes and contextually appropriate solution making (Cosens, et al., 2021), this chapter will emphasize skills that are required for enabling knowledge co-production in risk governance context. Importantly, the core focus will be on Trainers – trained to operate in the ‘complex problem space’ (Keating, et al., 2015:2944). As such, this document should not be treated as a blueprint replicated by each RWL. Instead, it presents **a collection** of theories, tools, and approaches **adaptable to diverse risk governance situations**. This applies to modules outlined later as well. Whilst they have been initially designed to align with the Risk-Tandem Framework, their exact content will be tailored to meet the needs of the RWLs.

It is also important to note that knowledge co-production processes themselves develop capacities (Bharwani, et al., 2024). By engaging in transdisciplinary settings (designed to facilitate continued learning across scales and disciplines, including non-traditional knowledge), users and providers develop their capacities and understanding regarding the use and uptake of knowledge in decision-making contexts (Daniels, et al., 2020; Bharwani, et al., 2024). As such, the Training of Trainers approach of DIRECTED approaches capacity development from a novel angle, going beyond lecture or lesson-based learning toward experiential learning and practical application of tools and mechanisms that promote continued reflection and sustained collaboration and innovation. Although “traditional” approaches will also be applied (accompanied by capacity needs assessments), capacity development under Phase 1. will begin with a focus on enabling knowledge co-production.

4.1 Capacities for knowledge co-production

Capacity development for knowledge co-production is a complex task. Skills required are rarely discussed in detail (Miller and Wyborn, 2020). Generally, some individual competencies can be outlined, including facilitation, trust building, communication, stakeholder engagement and knowledge brokering (Cvitanovic, et al., 2016). Others – such as networking, motivational skills, capability to understand the decision-making context, or how to influence it are specific to individual and often increase with experience (Djenontin and Meadow, 2018). Many of these skills are not bound to generate results either; partnerships, trust and communication are two-way streets, and often contingent upon the partners’ interest to collaborate on problems (Hutchins, et al., 2013). Thus, capacity development must be innovative and multifaceted to enable knowledge co-production.

More generally the issue of capacity development is further complicated by the lack of shared definitions in the context of DRR, CCA and risk governance. As pointed out by Hagelsteen and Becker (2014:298) in the context of DRR, there is no shared definition for the term capacity. In the realm of “practice”, capacity development can refer to almost anything, in the absence of shared understanding, standards and best practices. These issues are made worse by lack of academic research targeting capacity development and DRR (Scott, et al., 2014; Hagelsteen and Burke, 2016). Under DIRECTED (seeking to support the integration of DRR and CCA through knowledge co-production), understanding of skills required to advance such ambitions must be clearly outlined and discussed with stakeholders.

Based on section 2 and other complementary literature, it is possible to outline capacities to support knowledge co-production toward integrated DRM, CCA and complex risk management (in alignment with Risk-Tandem). Importantly, these should not be approached as a blueprint for knowledge gain, but as an emergent property that is nurtured through ‘flexible, adaptive and locally driven process of change and learning’ (Hagelsteen and Becker, 2019:9). Table 1 compiles process-based capacities that can support the leveraging of existing knowledges to instigate shifts in science-science/ science-society relations, mobilize others and bridge connections, instead of hard skills alone (Steen and Tuurnas, 2018:83). These interlinked aspects can be summarized as follows (whilst keeping in mind that tenets of co-production are integrated within each)

CAPACITIES	COMPETENCIES	TANDEM PHASE	REFERENCE
1. Transdisciplinary collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Convening and facilitation stakeholder engagement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building trust Negotiation and conflict management 	Scoping and Review	Cvitanovic and Meadow (2018); Daniels, et al., (2020); Bharwani, et al., (2024); Norström, et al., (2020); Fisher and Jasny (2017); Orsini, et al., (2019)
2. Research skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative methods: Surveys, interviews, focus group discussion Data management and analysis 	All	Daniels, et al. (2020)
3. Systems thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding complexity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coping with uncertainty Methods for holistic risk analyses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario-development 	Scoping and Review, Co-exploration	Cosens, et al. (2021); Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., (2024); Mckenzie, et al., (2009), Hagelsteen and Becker (2019), Orsini, et al., (2019)
4. Creative methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experimental methods: the use of play, games, and art Understanding empathy and emotion in decision-making 	Co-Exploration, Co-Design	Norström, et al, (2020); Daniels, et al., (2020)
5. Reflexivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring, evaluation and learning of knowledge co-production Adaptive governance and unlearning 	All	Bharwani, et al., (2024); Berkes, et al., (2017); Norström, et al. (2020)
6. Knowledge integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cross-disciplinary understanding for DRR and CCA and risk management Knowledge brokering and synthesis 	Co-Design, Integrating new knowledge and partners	Berkes, et al., (2017); Daniels, et al., (2020); Bharwani, et al., (2024)
7. Influencing change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advocacy Communication (dissemination, media engagement story-telling) 	Integrating new knowledge and partners	Lauta, et al., (2018)
8. Technical competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>“Hard skills” for risk governance, including risk assessment methodologies, understanding modelling, or risk layering.</i> 	All	

Table 1: Capacities for enabling knowledge co-production in risk governance contexts.

However, these are capacities identified in relation to knowledge co-production and the Tandem framework. It should be kept in mind that **additional capacity needs may emerge** during DIRECTED through capacity needs assessments and consultations with RWLs, and capacities as identified in Table 1. must be modified following the capacity needs assessments. Considering the iterative approach, the intention of (Risk)-Tandem is to enable knowledge co-production and continue identifying capacity development needs to support progressing through its four phases.

Alongside capacities, it is also important to examine **capacity levels** (Figure 6) in relation to expected impact of capacity development. This capacity development strategy focuses on **the individual level (Trainers and hosts of RWLs)**. Considering that they are experts of the DRM/ CCA structures, policies, budgets, strategies and frameworks of their setting, the intention is to leverage existing skills and knowledge to contextualize DIRECTED co-production and risk governance ambitions via locally led application of gained knowledges (and Risk-Tandem tools) without overtaking or overshadowing local priorities. After all, capacity development is usually most effective when it is built upon existing capacity (UNDRR, 2018), such as specialized and organizational knowledges.

To premise MEL, there is a need to highlight how individuals can enable change at the organizational level (through RWLs) as they use gained knowledges to navigate and influence their operational context, potentially influencing broader systems like rules, laws, policies, and financing. Institutional capacity development and strengthening can also be supported by measuring and improving the performance of organizations.

However, strengthening capacities as outlined above cannot be achieved with one-off training, but require a **set of interlinked and complimentary activities** from training to workshops, learning materials and sustained effort to engage (e.g., mentoring and communication between training etc.). This approach will be outlined further in sections below. In addition, institutionalization of knowledge will contribute to this aim beyond short-term training and workshops, through structured learning modules. That is, activities outlined in this strategy will be linked to the knowledge transfer plan (D6.3) and disseminated via the identified e-Learning platform for up-scaling and transferring knowledge regarding DIRECTED efforts.

Figure 6: Capacity levels (based on UNDRR, 2018).

All capacity development activities will be guided by the premise of triple loop learning, which can be put to practice through methods of co-production (Cosens, et al., 2021). DIRECTED aims to train hosts of the **RWLs to become** boundary-spanning **applied trans-disciplinarians** (Cosens, et al., 2021) or **learning champions** (Johannessen, et al., 2019) capable of simultaneously understanding and navigating their contexts with stakeholders involved, and the complexity these interactions generate. All training will emphasize facilitating triple loop learning (Figure 7) in their DRR/ CCA contexts, in efforts to contribute drive change in **organizational risk governance context** in a manner that deviates from simplistic risk management approaches. Eventually, this has potential for triggering change at an organizational level (assuming that the skills and capacities are applied consistently in RWLs).

Figure 7: Three loops of learning.

4.2 Capacity needs assessments

To further develop and refine capacities for knowledge co-production in risk governance contexts, and to identify further capacity needs among RWL Hosts-as-Trainers, this strategy requires a robust and practical approach to regular needs assessments. Linking to Milestone 19 (scoping consultations with RWLs and mapping of capacity needs) and associated task 4.2. (RWL comparison and assessment of needs), this process has been integrated into the (Risk)-Tandem process, conducted during months 9-36 (p11 of the Grant Agreement). Capacity needs assessments begin during Phase 1: Foundation (2023) seeking to support RWLs in establishing their labs, and to enable knowledge co-production during the first risk/governance scoping workshops during 2023 and early 2024. Recognizing the need for iterative approach that remains responsive to emerging needs, the first assessment takes the form of a semi-structured interview for general scoping purposes (annex 3). During following phases, they will be more formalized and structured for the purposes of cultivating a robust and measurable knowledge base (annex 4), developed based on lessons learned and refined with RWL hosts. It is also noted that capacities also differ across administrative levels, across sectors and persons involved in DRR and CCA (Becker, 2012). Anticipating the need to develop the capacities of trainers to train stakeholders in RWLs, upcoming capacity needs assessments may be refined to also cover stakeholders beyond the Hosts-as-Trainers, depending on the emerging needs and priorities.

4.3 Modules and T (phase 1, Foundation)

Phase 1., the Foundation of DIRECTED begins the process of applying Tandem to RWLs (T4.1) within Risk-Tandem, informed by capacity needs assessment and consultations, tailored support (T4.2) and online learning modules (D4.1) toward enabling knowledge co-production in risk governance contexts. Online modality was selected partly due to limitations of the project budget and geographical distances, but also because it was outlined as the preferred choice of the RWL hosts as identified in the D6.3 Knowledge Transfer Gaps and Opportunities Assessment (Figure 8):

Figure 8: Q11 regarding the DIRECTED training delivery, covering the entire project consortium.

Initially the focus of capacity development activities will focus on enabling knowledge co-production and understanding of risks from the perspective of complexity (linking to capacities as outlined in Table 1), thus beginning knowledge co-production in the RWLs (Figure 9). The first activities will be informed by the challenges as described under D.1.1. emerging needs as identified in scoping consultations and assessments. Delivered as a combination of lecture-based online modules, in-person training activities (under the General Assembly of 2023) and regular meetings, these begin forming the foundations for knowledge co-production and the implementation of (Risk)-Tandem, complimented by the Tandem guiding questions that seek to inform each step and associated training (annex 2).

Figure 9: Timeline: Phase 1. modules and potential modules for 2024-2026.

Full literature reviews, learning materials and descriptions will be provided with each module as they will be developed during Q3-Q4 of 2023 and Q1-Q2 of 2024. Foundation modules will be aligned with the Risk-Tandem phases, although they can be implemented iteratively, and returned to depending on the needs of the RWLs since they are progressing at different speeds. Delivered as a combination of formal capacity development and learning modules, tailored consultations with Real World Lab (RWL) hosts, guidance notes, and webinars, the first module series introduces aspects critical to the Risk-Tandem. Importantly, the first year is more iterative, in anticipation of the flexibility and adaptivity required for setting up RWLs.

I. Complex risks, integrated risk management and knowledge co-production

An entry to (Risk-)Tandem and its transdisciplinary application, including practical methods to map and understand complex risks and the centrality of knowledge co-production. Provides an overview of the WP 4/WP 3 joint approach and provides tools for risk scoping to establish preliminary boundary conditions for risk management with local stakeholders. This links to capacities 3, 6 and 8 identified in Table 1. It involves practical exercises (e.g., on Miro) that can be easily transferred to workshops in RWLs and covers aspects regarding risk management beyond hazards themselves (emphasizing the interconnectedness of hazards, socio-economic context, vulnerabilities, and climate change).

II. Facilitation skills and interactive workshop design (Engaging stakeholders)

To support interactive stakeholder engagement for co-production (Norström, et al., 2020), to create incentives for stakeholder participation, and to ensure sustained commitment as described in the SHIELD (Lauta, et al., 2018), RWLs must be supported in workshop design and facilitation (Annex VIII). This will be provided via continuous engagement, guidance notes, and individualised discussions with RWL hosts, responding to emerging needs by tailoring consultations for workshop design. This is required since facilitators must think on their feet, using knowledge, skills, and judgement to activate co-production activities in their contexts (Sicilia, et al., 2019).

Procedural factors emphasized to support this will, for example, provide guidance for preparing workshops, conflict resolution, or enabling trust, demonstrated via practical exercises that explore the challenges of facilitation in action. It will also elaborate (often overlooked) factors that cause co-production to fail – including unequal power relations and depoliticization, and how these could be managed (Turnhout, et al., 2020). Although socio-political disparities are often beyond the immediate control of facilitators, it is possible to mitigate them, for instance via informed participation recruitment that reduces selection bias (Maria Francesca, et al., 2019). The materials and lessons learned will be packaged into a learning module for future up-scaling.

III. Stakeholder Identification and mapping

This learning component will focus on **stakeholder identification and mapping** (linking to capacities 1 & 7). Building upon the Risk-Tandem phase 1. and its guiding questions on identifying and engaging relevant stakeholders, this phase guides the formation of the RWLs toward transdisciplinary RWLs. It provides a clear and realistic approach to stakeholder inclusion, with clearly defined and agreed upon roles that seek to nurture long-term partnerships (Lauta, et al., 2018). Capacity development will be delivered jointly with WP 3 in the form of tailored consultations, guidance notes and research support, organised jointly with RWLs. Guidance for cross-scale stakeholder engagement is foundational when assessing complex sustainability, climate, or risk issues which necessitate widening the scope of hierarchical approaches by involving actors across disciplines and levels of governance to include all relevant persons whose expertise, values, and concerns matter in the decision-making context (McKay, et al., 2017; Berkes, 2017). The materials and lessons learned will be packaged into a learning module for future up-scaling.

IV. Serious games and creative methods

Organised as a part of the General Assembly of 2023 in Cologne, this capacity development activity will emphasize on the use of serious games and creative/interactive methods for understanding and unpacking risk governance challenges (led by WP 3 and WP 4), in efforts to support early scoping of Phase 1. Designed as “learn-by-doing” sessions, the RWL hosts and project partners will partake in a modified Breaking of Silos game, intended to simulate the complexity of decision-making in a multi-hazard, multi-actor setting (underpinned by competing interests, limited funding, and uncertainty). This will also lay foundations for developing a tailored approach to co-designing interdisciplinary serious games for risk governance during DIRECTED.

Delivered in the form of tailored consultations and guidance notes, this component of capacity development seeks to support Hosts-as-Trainers in research associated with enabling knowledge co-production in their RWLs. This may include guidance for interviews and focus group discussions, data collection and analysis, and other emerging research needs. It is delivered jointly with WP 3.

V. Research skills

Delivered jointly with WP 3, this phase also provided guidance for RWL hosts for stakeholder identification and scoping to support the establishing of labs for knowledge co-production, guidance on conducting focus group discussions, and an introduction to the Risk-Tandem Framework to support its further application in a co-productive mode. Guidance notes and activities associated with these can be found under D3.1 (annex 2-5).

4.4 Phases 2, 3 and 4

Capacity development modules for RWL hosts-as-trainers will support them in facilitating workshops in a co-productive mode and help them in addressing capacity gaps that may affect the operation of the RWLs (such as training RWL stakeholders on citizen engagement, or specific risk assessment methodologies). Under phases 2, 3 and 4 (aspects of which can be returned to if necessary), a more structured capacity needs assessment and consultations will be arranged and delivered regularly (see Annex 4), linked to the “co-production baseline” as identified through these engagements. This is done to fully align core modules and needs-based modules with contextual needs in each RWL, based on their priorities and emerging needs during phase 2 (co-exploration of risks and governance challenges) phase 3 (co-production of risk governance solutions) and during the phase 4 (up-scaling and sustaining them).

While the primary focus remains on the Trainers, there's flexibility to offer training to stakeholders, consistent with Risk-Tandem and related guidelines (developed jointly with WP 3 and WP 5). This continues Task 4.2 (comparison and assessment of needs through learning, capacity development and knowledge exchange, M9-M36, that will be completed toward the end of 2025. However, since the exact capacity development needs for Trainers and stakeholders after the initial first phases of Risk-Tandem are uncertain, and vary among RWLs, the module contents will be developed and refined iteratively based on needs assessment and complementary research later. Only a suggestion (aligned with the Tandem and Risk-Tandem guiding questions) can be presented here, linked to the expected needs emerging from the processes of co-exploring risks, and co-producing risk management solutions based on this knowledge.

5 Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning

At a macro level, the DIRECTED Project seeks to improve the practical management and efficiency of managing disaster risk, disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation. The proposal outlines the way to achieve this as through “the development of [...] appropriate governance frameworks that improve joint working, provide replicable workflow processes, and enable management of complexity [...] to improve current working practices. Likewise, the interoperability and integration of multiple analytical tools needs to be developed to increase access and efficiency to multiple forms of hazard data and tools in risk assessment. Developing a data ecosystem that enables communication of relevant information to multiple partners and enables the access to multiple forms of data and results is critical to increasing a joined up and rapid approach to DRM/ CCA management.” This in essence summarizes the project’s Theory of Change (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Directed Theory of Change – impacts, outcomes, and beneficiaries.

For the purposes of WP 4, the objective of MEL is two-fold, covering: 1) the impact of capacity development activities for knowledge co-production in RWLs, and; 2) the outcomes of knowledge co-production processes in RWLs. The latter will be assessed independently but linking the contributions of knowledge co-production toward strengthened risk governance and the Risk-Tandem application (Task 1.3), as well as the contributions toward overall DIRECTED impact in its scientific, societal and economic dimensions (Figure 10).

5.1 MEL for Training of Trainers

For DIRECTED, the MEL for ToT will be enhanced by establishing a unified evaluation framework based on capacity needs assessments, and negotiated with other stakeholders (Dahler-Larsen, 2018). There is a need to establish a clear and transparent local link between the co-production intervention strategy and expected outcomes, in efforts to assess whether this link between the two holds (Brix, et al., 2020; Visman, et al., 2022). This cannot be done without establishing and operationalizing context-specific outcome indicators for ToT alongside those identified in table 1, given that co-production is and will be dependent on individual and organizational, sometimes spontaneous acts (Pestoff, 2014). Although the process of co-evaluation with stakeholders across the levels of governance is challenging due to issues of power and differing perspectives (Brix, et al., 2020), it is foundational for generating an understanding of the success of co-production as perceived and deemed effective from and by the grass-root levels. Furthermore, a robust MEL plan can help in improving co-production and, thus improve its expected outcomes (Visman, et al., 2022).

Consequently, a MEL plan for ToT will be firstly developed at the individual level, through collaboration with the RWL hosts. Durose, et al., (2017) et al., propose utilizing a process of ‘appreciative inquiry’ as a way of distilling experiences, memories, and perspectives of individuals through interviews and other methods (such as key informant interviews and surveys) to collectively identify critical elements of success. If combined with a contribution analysis, it is possible to begin assessing change over time, especially when the evaluation purpose, key questions, indicators, and plans are negotiated with stakeholders throughout the process (ibid). This aspect of MEL covers knowledge and skills gained at the individual levels, conducted with RWL Hosts-as-Trainers. It will begin with capacity needs assessments forming a baseline for knowledge co-production in risk governance contexts, the first of which will be delivered through consultations that assess and identify needs for RWL co-production workshops in 2023, alongside a capacity needs assessment in an interview format. Following each workshop, the facilitators will be given a self-evaluation sheet (annex 6) where they can reflect on their performance and the usefulness of capacity development training in facilitating knowledge co-production, and any challenges they may have faced. In addition, each workshop will also be followed by a structured debrief consultation (arranged jointly by WP 4 and WP 3). This approach was selected to adequately incorporate the reflections, perceptions and experiences of RWL Hosts-as-Trainers in the MEL, thus supporting the co-design of reporting regarding successes and challenges.

In phases 2 (Growth), 3 (Learn) and 4 (Sustain), a more structured approach is required, as the RWLs become formalized and begin implementing Risk-Tandem and knowledge co-production beyond scoping and relationship-building (Figure 11). For this purpose, a more robust capacity needs assessment questionnaire has been developed (annex 4), to be revised and implemented annually. Additionally, capacity development modules beyond the first phase will be followed by an evaluation (annex 5) to assess the knowledge gain and benefits to RWL activities, in relation to capacities as identified in table 1. Scoping consultations, workshop planning support, debriefs and self-evaluation will resume as previously (also supported by complimentary research and other risk governance activities as detailed in

D3.1). MEL on ToT will be used to inform the iterative co-design and co-development of modules for knowledge co-production in risk governance contexts (D4.1). and the updating of the Tandem process and framework (D4.4).

Figure 11: Components of MEL for Training of Trainers and capacity development.

5.2 MEL for co-production Outcomes

Linking to the impacts of capacity development, the other dimension that requires monitoring are knowledge co-production outcomes (T1.2., M3-6), in relation to the contributions of WP 4 and RWL activities toward wider DIRECTED outcomes. For this purpose, WP 4 has developed a methodology for collecting and analyzing data for assessing knowledge co-production under DIRECTED, discussed in detail here. Outcomes of knowledge co-production will be reported via milestones 3-6 (periodic report on the knowledge co-production outcomes), which further detail this methodology.

In the absence of widely accepted and empirically evidenced methodologies for monitoring knowledge co-production (Miller and Wyborn, 2020; Bandola-Gill, et al., 2021), WP 4 MEL will build upon “good principles” as identified by Norström, et al. (2020), combined with the coded Tandem questions (annex 2) serving as a best-practice guide (Figure 13). This integration was done to provide more structure to themes as they alone do not cover enough detail for developing and co-designing contextually appropriate indicators for successful knowledge co-production.

Figure 12: Good principles for co-production, elaborated through Tandem guiding questions for the purposes of MEL. Questions have been redacted from the coding for illustrative purposes.

As per Figure 12, each “good principle” will be further categorized through Tandem codes to qualitatively measure and demonstrate improvements in risk governance processes as achieved via knowledge co-production. In particular, the interest of WP 4 is to demonstrate the quality and impact of knowledge co-production processes in relation to the status quo, to assess the degree to which collaborative, transdisciplinary, and creative stakeholder methods can support holistic risk governance and the integration of DRM and CCA toward increased resilience and sustainability.

Using the approach WP 4 has developed for data coding and analysis through (primarily) deductive assessment of data emerging from the RWLs (including consultation transcripts, notes, interview results, workshop debriefs, self-reflection evaluations, user stories of WP 5, and so on), all RWL data will be coded and analyzed under the four good principal categories, structured via the Tandem guiding questions (Annex 7, demonstrating the coding approach). This will be linked to objectives for knowledge co-production in RWLs (co-identified with RWL hosts) which are reported and measured in Milestones 3-6 outlining the progress toward achieving them. These milestones will also capture the reflections and perceptions of hosts regarding the outcomes (and challenges) of knowledge co-production in RWLs, in efforts to inform the development of future activities and capacity development.

For assessing (and learning from) qualitative evidence, a contribution analysis will be utilized; an approach that examines cause-effects through a mixed-method theory-based evaluation that can infer (instead of attribute) causation (Brix, et al., 2020). This is especially useful for analyzing the outcomes of co-production programs consisting of complex and interacting variables which, in essence, constitute a social phenomenon (ibid). Whereas attribution analysis would focus on simple and technical problems or products (such as the Data Fabric), ToT and RWL activities require a thorough mixed method ‘contribution story’ (Funnell and

Rogers, 2011), that does not necessarily represent ultimate truths, but instead offers reasoning why, and sufficient conclusion of how co-production interventions have contributed to given outcomes in ambiguous contexts (Dahler-Larsen, 2018; Brix, et al., 2020; Visman, et al., 2022).

This approach was designed in acknowledgement of the intangible nature of knowledge co-production. Since these processes emphasize change in terms of processes and relationships, capacities, confidence and collaborations as well as communication across the landscape of actors (Daniels, et al., 2020; Brandsen, et al., 2018; McEvoy, et al., 2016), evaluating 'performance' must leverage adaptive approaches that capture information that is often intangible and beyond linear results chains (McEvoy, et al., 2016). In the context of DIRECTED, it is thus not enough to measure the number of software developed and trainings delivered, or reports, plans, policies, and roadmaps produced, simply because such indicators do not lend themselves to understanding subtle, underlying or process-based changes, nor the impacts they may have had.

6 Links to other DIRECTED activities

6.1 Links to Risk-Tandem (WP 3)

As evident throughout this strategy, knowledge co-production and capacity development are the primary means through which Risk-Tandem tools and approaches are implemented in the labs. For this purpose, WP 3 provides guidance and support for assessing and strengthening risk governance activities, and WP 4 translates these into capacity development when needed to support their implementation. Much of this work is shared and seamlessly integrated across WP 3, WP 4, and when necessary for the purposes of the Data Fabric (to understand and map for instance, user needs through co-exploration), WP 5. For engagement with WP 1 and the RWLs, see section below.

6.2 Links to RWLs (WP 1)

Through continuous engagement, consultations and capacity development, WP 4 and WP 1 are closely aligned in the implementation of knowledge co-production (and the Risk-Tandem approach). This collaboration informs capacity development to ensure that activities are always aligned with RWL needs, and that the iterative application of knowledge co-production is implemented in a manner that is realistic and feasible (and thus, achievable), in efforts to achieve the project's intended outcomes.

6.3 Links to knowledge transfer

Aligning with D6.3., modules as discussed in this strategy are designed and refined in a manner that supports the further replication of DIRECTED capacity development (and the Risk-Tandem approach) in other contexts, through the dissemination of modules. See D6.3 for the plan on knowledge transfer.

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Annex I: Tandem guiding questions

The Tandem framework consists of a structured set of elements (or four phases) that seek to inform actors toward structuring transdisciplinary engagement, interaction and collaborative learning. Each phase is accompanied by practical guiding questions, seeking to lay foundations for facilitating deeper discussions regarding shared challenges, risks, goals, governance, communication, data or information needs as well as capacities. The guiding questions are available via the following link:

<https://weadapt.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/Tandem-Guidance-2024-final.pdf>

Annex II: Preliminary capacity needs assessment

This capacity needs assessment seeks to establish the early capacity needs of RWL hosts for facilitating the co-production of multi-hazard risk governance in their country contexts, as a continuation of the D1.2 (capacity development strategy). As such, it maps existing capacities and seeks to identify further needs for capacity development for implementing Risk-Tandem, i.e., skills required for facilitating complex multi-hazard risk governance through the lens of co-production, for integrating DRR and CCA, and for enforcing interoperability. Additionally, it will scope potential technical capacity needs required to support this process, although they are mapped in more detail under T2.1. and associated D2.1. (Stocktake on Interoperability) which also includes a questionnaire on interoperability needs.

In addition, it should be noted that this preliminary needs assessment is only a part of a larger comparative efforts focusing on RWL needs under Tasks 4.2, seeking to complement other work. As per the task description, it builds on the findings of the D1.1. (RWL Description and Set Up) as well as on the results of the co-production workshops to discuss and explore the RWL context, arranged during the project consortium meeting in Cologne. Later, the policy context and institutional landscape will be analysed by WP 3 partners as a part of Milestone 3.2. Together, these will aid in developing locally owned and contextually appropriate training materials and modules for facilitating co-production that will help addressing real-world challenges facing complex risk and climate challenges.

Risk management

- What hazards are currently being addressed/focused on in your Real World Lab?
- What is your current capacity to assess the hazard/risk situation, including its relationship to climate change and uncertainty?
- In relation to above, what is your current capacity to apply methods of co-production to assess the risk situation and develop solutions through transdisciplinary engagement?
- In your experience, how well are considerations for vulnerability and vulnerability reduction integrated into your working context? (1-5)?
- How would you rank your capacity to integrate vulnerability reduction into planning?
- How would you rank your (or your RWL stakeholders') capacities to influence DRR/CCA policy at national/regional levels (1-5)?
- In your experience, would you say transboundary risks are considered and integrated into planning in your context? (Yes/no).
- How would you rank your capacity to plan and implement monitoring and evaluation (in particular, M&E for workshops and meetings) (1-5)?
- How would you rank your capacity to analyse data from M&E (1-5)?

Communication and stakeholder engagement

- Do you consider your RWL to be transdisciplinary (involving representation from science-policy-practice working in DRR and CCA, and includes citizens/communities or representatives of vulnerable groups)?
- Who is missing and why? (describe).
- What are your biggest challenges in terms of communicating with stakeholders? (Describe)
- How would you assess your capacity to communicate risk information to non-expert audiences?
- How would you assess your capacity to communicate climate uncertainty to non-expert audiences?

Finance

- How would you rank your capacity to budget, manage and implement activities and to mobilize resources (for DRR/CCA planning) (1-5)?
- there support for transdisciplinary engagement in your context beyond DIRECTED? I.e., is funding available for workshops, for funding cross-agency projects and collaboration? (Yes/no).
- Do you have agency and influence over resources available to you? I.e., are budget decisions made elsewhere? (yes/no)
- How severe are the financial constraints affecting your work (rank 1-5)?
- Does your RWL include persons with influence over budgeting and fiscal planning regarding DRR and CCA? (yes/no).

Data and interoperability

- Do you consider data interoperability a critical issue and an immediate priority in your working context?
- What are these priorities (describe)?
- How would you rank your ability to work with hazard/climate data and models (1-5) stakeholders.

Facilitation skills

- How would you rank your current capacity to arrange RWL meetings (1-5)?
- How would you rank your capacity to facilitate co-production through engaging activities, innovating workshop sessions, simulations, serious games, or themes for world café sessions (1-5)?
- How would you rank your capacity to facilitate energisers (1-5)?

-
- What is your current capacity to manage/resolve conflict and arguments between stakeholders?
 - In your opinion, what is the biggest challenge for facilitation the co-production of risk governance in your governance context? (describe)

Feedback

- Have you found the work WP 3 and WP 4 useful so far? (describe)
- How can it improve? (describe)

Annex III: Structured needs assessment

This capacity needs assessment represents an elaboration of the semi-structured interviews, conducted and revised annually to identify address emerging needs and RWL priorities. Although linked to capacities as detailed in table 1. (and the Risk-Tandem implementation in general), this draft should not be treated as the final product, but instead a foundation for capacity needs assessments, modules, and MEL for capacity development.

Introduction

As part of the capacity development for RWL hosts, this assessment seeks to identify and support the analysis of current work-flows and risk governance in DRR/CCA contexts toward improved integration. It was drafted to help determine the capacity needs and gaps for RWL hosts to develop during the capacity development. Building on the capacity development needs identified in this capacity needs assessment, trainings will be planned and designed to support capacity development of RWL hosts/trainers in co-production. The capacity needs assessments will be conducted throughout the DIRECTED project, to help inform future capacity development training.

2. Questionnaires

There will be one questionnaire (capacity needs assessment) asked to RWL hosts before their RWL workshops. For evaluation purposes, this will be combined with the Co-production Capacity Development MEL questionnaires DIRECTED following capacity development activities.

Consent: Adhering to GDPR rules, all survey responses are confidential. We collect specific identity details only to help understand the demographic we have reached. The data from this survey will be used for scientific purposes within the DIRECTED project. The analysis of the survey data will be therefore anonymous and aggregated.

Please confirm the following statements* (MCQ):

I have read and understood the information provided above. I voluntarily consent to participate in this survey. Yes No

I consent to the processing of my anonymous data for research purposes* (SOQ) Yes No

I confirm that I am 18 years or older* (SOQ) Yes No

A) Background questions:

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
1	Name	OQ	NA	NA
2	Job role/title	OQ	NA	NA
3	Role within RWLs	SOQ	Host; Participant; Facilitator	NA
4	Sector	SOQ	Research; Practitioner; I/NGO; Academia; Private; Civil service; Labourer	NA
5	Gender	SOQ	Female; Male; Other; Prefer not to say	NA

B) Questionnaire before capacity development

Questions on knowledge co-production

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
6	Do you know what “co-production” is?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	NA
6a	Please select the statement which best defines “co-production”	SOQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An iterative and collaborative process involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways toward sustainable future. A process that ensures participants work individually and separately on a project, with limited interaction between participants. A process that highlights the best ways to work with stakeholders and stakeholders are encouraged to agree without providing feedback. 	Select “Yes” to Q6 above.

7	Have you done any co-production work previously?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	If select “Yes” to Q7 and “No” or “Not sure” to Q6 pop-up asking if they’re sure
8	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
8a	How is your knowledge of co-production?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8b	How confident are you at leading an activity in a workshop?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8c	How confident are you in leading an activity at a workshop if it is a co-production activity?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9	Please select the correct definition for the following terms, relating to co-production			
9a	Stakeholder engagement	SOQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The actions, processes and procedures relating to engaging stakeholders. • Communications are led from the stakeholders who reach out to the project to ask to be involved. • The actions and processes related to ensuring people are unaware of the project and do not engage. 	NA
9b	Capacities	SOQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard and soft human capacities (knowledge and skills) required. • Plans to complete a project successfully. • Worst case scenario plans for a projects. 	NA
9c	Knowledge integration	SOQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversification of available knowledge beyond a single discipline or epistemology, 	NA

			<p>and their combination toward holistic understanding.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring only one key knowledge discipline is considered and used as the main focus. • Everyone contributes and co-produces information. 	
10	Please identify the benefits of co-production	MCQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased buy-in and ownership • Useful feedback and solutions • Excess feedback and solutions • Lack of buy-in and ownership • Builds on peoples existing capabilities • Breaks down barriers • Strengthens peer support networks • Builds mutuality and reciprocity • Builds gaps in knowledge • Builds barriers between people • Weakens communication and support networks • Creates separate work streams 	NA
11	Please identify the challenges of co-production	MCQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of engagement • Too much engagement • Limited facilitation in workshops • Too much facilitation in workshops • Stakeholder fatigue • Lack of time to complete work 	NA

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Too much time taken to complete work • Language barriers • Limited capacity • Communication challenges • Coordination challenges • Lack of resources 	
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General

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
12	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
12a	How would you rate your understanding of risk?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12b	How confident are you in explaining the concept of risk to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12c	How would you rate your understanding of risk governance?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12d	How confident are you in explaining the concept of risk governance to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12e	How would you rate your understanding of risk management?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12f	How confident are you in explaining the concept of risk management to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12g	How would you rate your understanding of	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA

	stakeholder engagement?			
12h	How confident are you in explaining the concept of stakeholder engagement to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12i	How would you rate your understanding of project financials?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12j	How confident are you in explaining the concept of project financials to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12k	How would you rate your understanding of data interoperability?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12l	How confident are you in explaining the concept of data interoperability to participants in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
12m	How would you rate your facilitation skills?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
13	Please put in order the topics you would like capacity development training on, with the highest priority first.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk and risk governance • Co-production and transdisciplinary collaboration • Risk management • Communication and stakeholder engagement • Finance • Data interoperability • Facilitation skills 	NA
14	What else do you hope to learn from the capacity development?	OQ	NA	NA

Annex IV: Evaluation questionnaire

1. Introduction

The capacity development focuses on the hosts who guide and enable co-production of knowledge and solutions for multi-hazard risk governance in their country contexts, as a continuation of the D1.2 (capacity development strategy). The outcomes of the capacity development is to support the RWL hosts to plan, facilitate, and co-produce workshops within the RWLs. This is an immediate short-term outcome of the capacity development; however, this should also have longer term impacts and outcomes for the DIRECTED project. Capacity of the RWL hosts is being conducted through online workshops and trainings.

Building on the capacity development needs identified in the capacity needs assessment, trainings have been planned and designed to support capacity development of RWL hosts/trainers in co-production. The capacity needs assessments will be conducted throughout the DIRECTED project, to help inform future capacity development training. Specific sections of the tables below will be selected depending on the theme and topic.

2. Aim

This M&E questionnaire on the capacity development will be carried out to identify the effectiveness of the capacity development and gather feedback from RWL hosts to learn and improve performance of the capacity development.

3. Questionnaires

There will be four questionnaires in total to monitor the success of the capacity development training in all dimensions of DIRECTED in relation to knowledge co-production in risk governance contexts. These will include:

- RWL host questionnaire before capacity development
- Co-production knowledge questions
- RWL host questionnaire after capacity development
- Capacity development feedback
- Capacity needs assessment
- Risk and risk governance
- Co-production and transdisciplinary collaborate
- Risk management
- Communication and stakeholder engagement

- Finance
- Data
- Facilitation skills
- RWL host questionnaire after RWL
- Capacity development feedback
- RWL stakeholder questionnaire after RWL

4. Questionnaire codes

Survey content: (SOQ: Select one question, OQ: Open question, MCQ: Multiple choice question)

5. Effectiveness indicators

A) Training reaction

Indicator	How to measure	Measurement
RWL hosts participation rate	Observation	100% participate
RWL hosts completion rate	Observation	100% complete
RWL hosts satisfaction score	Questionnaire immediately after training	80% satisfaction
RWL hosts acquired knowledge/skill	Questionnaire immediately before training, after training, and after RWL	80% knowledge/skill improved
RWL hosts increased learning score	Questionnaire immediately after training	80% participants had an average of 4+ increased knowledge
RWL hosts satisfaction score	Questionnaire immediately after training	80% participants had an average of 4+ satisfaction
RWL hosts acquired knowledge/skill	Questionnaire immediately after training	80% participants had an average of 4+ knowledge/skill improved

B) RWL perspectives

Indicator	How to measure	Measurement
RWL stakeholders	Observation	80% participate

participation rate		
RWL stakeholders completion rate	Observation	80% complete
RWL stakeholders increased learning score	Questionnaire immediately after training	80% participants had an average of 4+ increased knowledge
RWL stakeholders satisfaction score	Feedback questionnaire from RWL stakeholders	80% participants had an average of 4+ satisfaction
RWL stakeholders acquired knowledge/skill	Questionnaire before and after learning, combined with capacity needs assessment	80% participants had an average of 4+ knowledge/skill improved

6. Questionnaire for RWL hosts

Background questions

	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
1	Name	OQ	NA	NA
2	Job role/title	OQ	NA	NA
3	Role within RWLs	SOQ	Host; Participant; Facilitator	NA
4	Sector	SOQ	Research; Practitioner; I/NGO; Academia; Private; Civil service; Labourer	NA
5	Gender	SOQ	Female; Male; Other; Prefer not to say	NA

Capacity development feedback

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
6	Where the aims of the capacity development clear?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	NA
6a	Please identify the top 3 key aims of the capacity development	MCQ (ranking)	<i>[answer options should be updated depending</i>	NA

			<i>on the RWLJ</i>	
7	Please list your key takeaways from the capacity development.	OQ	NA	NA
8	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
8a	How satisfied are you with the capacity development?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8b	Did you find the capacity development enjoyable?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8c	Was the capacity development conducted at the correct level of understanding?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8d	Do you feel you have learnt from the capacity development?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8e	Can you see the capacity development being useful longer term?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9	Do you have any additional comments on the capacity development?	OQ	NA	NA

Capacity needs

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
10	Do you remember completing a capacity needs assessment?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	NA
10a	Do you remember what information you included in the capacity development form?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	Only appears if selected "Yes" to Q9
10b	Did you find capacity training was tailored to areas you identified in the capacity needs assessment?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	Only appears if selected "Yes" to Q9 and Q9a
11	Do you have any additional comments on the capacity assessment or capacity development?	OQ	NA	NA

Knowledge co-production and transdisciplinary collaboration

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
12	Do you know what “co-production” is?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	NA
12a	Please select the statement which best defines “co-production”	SOQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An iterative and collaborative process involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways toward sustainable future. A process that ensures participants work individually and separately on a project, with limited interaction between participants. A process that highlights the best ways to work with stakeholders and stakeholders are encouraged to agree without providing feedback. 	Select “Yes” to Q6 above.
13	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
13a	How would you rate your understanding of co-production?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
13b	Do you think your understanding of co-production has increased from the capacity development training?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
13c	How satisfied are you with the capacity development training on co-production?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA

14	Are there further aspects of co-production you would like capacity development training on?	OQ	NA	NA
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Risk governance

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
15	What is your current understanding of the term “risk”?	OQ	NA	NA
16	What is your current understanding of the term “risk governance”?	OQ	NA	NA
17	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
17a	How would you rate your understanding of risk?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
17b	Do you think your understanding of risk has increased from the capacity development training?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
17c	How satisfied are you with the capacity development training on risk?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
17d	How would you rate your understanding of risk governance?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
17e	Do you think your understanding of risk governance has increased from the capacity development training?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
17f	How satisfied are you with the capacity development training on risk governance?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
18				
	Are there further aspects of risk or risk governance you would like capacity development training on?	OQ	NA	NA

Risk management

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
19	What is your understanding of the term “risk management”?	OQ	NA	NA
20	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
20a	How would you rate your understanding of risk management?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
20b	What is your understanding of risk management being addressed/focussed on in your RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
20c	Do you think your understanding of risk management has increased from the capacity development training?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
20d	How satisfied are you with the capacity development training on risk management?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
21	Are there further aspects of risk management you would like capacity development training on?	OQ	NA	NA

Communication and stakeholder engagement

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
22	What is your current understanding of the term “stakeholder engagement”?	OQ	NA	NA
23	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
23a	How would you rate your understanding of stakeholder engagement?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
23b	Do you think your understanding of stakeholder engagement has increased	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA

	from the capacity development training?			
23c	How satisfied are you with the capacity development training on stakeholder engagement?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
24	Are there further aspects of stakeholder engagement you would like capacity development training on?	OQ	NA	NA

Finance

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
25	What is your current understanding of the term “project financials”?	OQ	NA	NA
26	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
26a	How would you rate your understanding of project financials?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
26b	Do you think your understanding of project financials has increased from the capacity development training?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
26c	How satisfied are you with the capacity development training on project financials?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
27	Are there further aspects of project financials you would like capacity development training on?	OQ	NA	NA

Data interoperability

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
28	What is your current understanding of the	OQ	NA	NA

	term “data interoperability”?			
29	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
29a	How would you rate your understanding of data interoperability?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
29b	Do you think your understanding of data interoperability has increased from the capacity development training?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
29c	How satisfied are you with the capacity development training on data interoperability?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
30	Are there further aspects of data interoperability you would like capacity development training on?	OQ	NA	NA

Facilitation skills

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
31	What is your current understanding of facilitation skills?	OQ	NA	NA
32	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
32a	How would you rate your understanding of facilitation skills?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
32b	Do you think your understanding of facilitation skills has increased from the capacity development training?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
32c	How satisfied are you with the capacity development training on facilitation skills?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
33	Are there further aspects of facilitation skills you would like capacity development training on?	OQ	NA	NA

Feedback

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
6	Do you remember completing the capacity development on co-production?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	NA
7	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
7a	How satisfied are you with the capacity development?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
7b	Did you find the capacity development enjoyable?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
7c	Was the capacity development conducted at the correct level of understanding?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
7d	Do you feel you have learnt from the capacity development?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
7e	Can you see the capacity development being useful longer term?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
8a	How successful was your RWL for you?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8b	How satisfied are you with the capacity development before the RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8c	Did you find the capacity development relevant to the RWL?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
8d	Was the capacity development useful?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9	Are there further areas you would like capacity development training on?	OQ	NA	NA

Questionnaire for RWL stakeholders

Question Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options	Constraints
6	Where the aims of the training clear?	SOQ	Yes; No; Not sure	NA
7	Please identify the top 3 key aims of the training	MCQ (ranking)	<i>[answer options should be updated depending on the RWL]</i>	NA
8	Please list your key takeaways from the training.	OQ	NA	NA
9	Please rank the following information (1=lowest, 5=highest):			
9a	How satisfied are you with the training?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9b	Did you find the training enjoyable?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9c	Was the training conducted at the correct level of understanding?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9d	Do you feel you have learnt from the training?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9e	Can you see the training being useful longer term?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9f	How successful did you think the co-production method used in the training was?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
9g	How successful were the RWL hosts in leading the co-production method throughout the workshop?	SOQ	1;2;3;4;5	NA
10	Please provide any positive or constructive feedback for the RWL hosts.	OQ	NA	NA

Annex V: Host self-evaluation sheet

RWL host self-reflection sheet

[to be completed by RWL hosts (either individually or jointly) after RWL stakeholder workshops]

Name and organisation:

Real World Lab name:

Date of workshop/ activity:

Role: RWL host Directed partner support

List interactive/engagement approach(es) used e.g. world café, ice-breakers, game

My contribution

I did spend less time talking than the group members (<30% of time is Yes) Yes No

I did have a number of prompting questions prepared for each group discussion Yes No

I collected the relevant information from the group members Yes No

I encouraged everyone to contribute during the discussion Yes No

Rate your satisfaction with your performance under the following headings

	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Could be improved/ dissatisfied
My use of open and closed questions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My ability to ensure discussion wasn't dominated by 2/3 of participants	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My ability to generate a comfortable environment for participants	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My use of body language and tone	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My listening skills	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My ability to keep the discussion running smoothly	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

My approach to handling conflict during the meeting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My ability to reach consensus in the group discussion	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My debrief discussion with Directed colleagues	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

What went well?

What didn't work well?

Rate your satisfaction with Directed support on the following:

	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Could be improved/ dissatisfied
Print/digital materials (before workshop)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Presentation materials (during workshop)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Interactive / engagement tools/ approaches / guidance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Social-media/ public facing communication material	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sharing technical expertise during preparation and follow up meetings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

What support do you need from Directed in terms of facilitation and workshops? E.g. Training, guidance, documentation

Annex VI: Approach to qualitative coding and data analysis

Using a deductive approach (allowing patterns to emerge from the qualitative data) all RWL outputs from capacity needs assessments and interview transcripts to workshop debriefs, reports and other evidence will be coded using AtlasTI, complemented by literature reviews and codes derived from the (Risk)-Tandem Framework. This work has already begun using early consultations, self-evaluation sheets and other documentation as an exploratory baseline that will be developed further for future as more qualitative data emerges through workshops and stakeholder engagement in the RWLs. The codebook itself will not be attached here, but the methodology elaborating coding and analysis is visualized and explained in Figures VIII:1-7).

The analysis of the coded data will be supported by an approach combining good principles for knowledge co-production (Norström, et al, 2020) and Tandem questions (Daniels, et al., 2020; Bharwani, et al., 2024) to support analysis co-production in RWLs. In efforts to identify successes and challenges, the Tandem questions (considered as best practice principles) are arranged as indicators under the “good principles” that can be measured and assessed qualitatively, and through self-reported reflections from the RWL hosts. Implementation of this MEL (and associated indicators) will be continuously negotiated with hosts (and later, RWL stakeholders) to align them with the context, recognising that the approach as presented here may fall short in covering all aspects where positive change has been achieved in risk governance contexts (or in terms of integrating DRR and CCA).

Importantly, this evidence will be used to revise and refine the approach to capacity development and Training of Trainers, to inform the work of other work packages, and contributes to the periodic reporting on knowledge co-production outcomes (M3-6) as well as the refining of the Tandem framework (M15-19; D4.4).

User guide:

Note: AtlasTI does not allow three layers of sub-codes. Therefore, sub-code such as “planning/policy gap” cannot be categorized under its’ parent code “Policy and Planning”. If there is a need to read these side by side, user must tag both codes under co-occurrence analysis.

Code groups are not higher order codes. Instead, they acts as filters that support comparison of content across two different code groups.

Figure VIII:1: Coding guide for categorizing data on AtlasTi.

Figure VII:2: Risk governance codes emerging from qualitative data (Group 1).

Figure VII:3: Knowledge co-production codes emerging from qualitative data (Group 2).

Figure VII:4: Data-related codes emerging from qualitative data (Group 2).

Figure VII:5: Hazards, climate change, and vulnerability- related codes emerging from qualitative data (Group 2).

Data analysis

For the purposes of data analysis, the thematic “good principles” for knowledge co-production (Norström, et al., 2020) have been sub-divided into analysis categories by arranging the Tandem questions under each category (Figure VII:6). Codes as expressed under VII:1-5 will be analyzed and discussed in these dimensions to demonstrate and identify co-production successes, enablers and challenges for the purposes of DIRECTED reporting.

Tandem Element	MEL Element1	Theme	Sub-code	Impact code2
Scope, review identify and engage	Context-based	Risks, vulnerability and challenges (climate and non-climate)	Natural hazards/disaster risks	Holistic overview of risks and vulnerabilities.
			Climate and disaster risks	
			Non-climate/disaster risks	
			Socio-economic vulnerabilities	
	Context-based	Impacts	Natural hazards/disasters	Holistic overview of impacts.
			Environmental impacts	
			Climate and disaster impacts	
			Non-climate/disaster impacts	
	Pluralistic	Identified and engaged relevant actors and champions	Stakeholders relating to climate/risk information and data	Increased awareness and understanding of knowledge and stakeholder landscape.
			Stakeholders involved in decision-making process	
			Stakeholders vulnerable/at risk	
			Knowledge systems engaged with	Improved communication (e.g. trust, dialogue, co-production, language).
	Methods of			

			engagement used			
Co-explore	Goal-oriented	Co-explore challenges and goals	Socio-economic challenges (e.g. income, education)	Creating shared understanding - consensus building around priorities, where it was absent previously, for example.		
			Decision-making challenges (e.g. representation, responsibilities, data)			
			Communication challenges (e.g. language, terminology, channels)			
			Adaptation challenges (e.g. climate, social, economic, political, environmental)			
		Co-explore governance context	Windows of opportunity	Increased understand of governance levers of change.		
			Institutional capacity/arrangements			
			Existing plans, policies, and projects			
			Governance mechanism			
		Co-explore information needs	Funding	Increased awareness and understanding of challenges, risks, and impacts faced through enhanced understanding of the use and limits of data/models.		
			Appropriate format			
			Relevant language			
			Accessible terminology			
			Capacity to articulate needs			
					Information channel	

			Appropriate scales (relevant to temporal and spatial scales of decision)	
Co-design solutions	Co-explore and identify solutions		Relevant to decision context	Solutions that provide increased resilience to climate and disaster risk.
			Salience (priority need)	
			Credibility (trusted)	
	Appraise solutions		Preferences	Limiting interpretation due to underlying socio-cultural or technical assumptions. Creating prejudiced points of view.
			Uncertainty	
			Maladaptation	
			Compound risks	
			Cascading risks	
			Multiple hazards	
			Synergies or co-benefits	
		Trade-offs		
		Assumptions		
	Cognitive bias			
Co-design solutions		Applicability	Moving from useful to usable information.	
		Usability		
		Desired needs met		
Integrate new	Communication		Tailored communication of climate information	Increased/continuous information sharing and exchange.
			Tailored communication of non-climate information	
			Format	More open modes of collaboration/communication.
			Language	
			Terminology	

knowledge and partners	Interactive		Capacity		
			Information channel		
		Capacity development	Capacities		Increased capacity and confidence of both providers and users of disaster and climate risk information.
			Confidence building		
			Increased understanding of the decision context		
			Increased understanding of the use and limits of climate information.		
		Partnership development	Strengthened relationships, partnerships and networks		Increased access to resources (e.g. information/networks/models).
		Financing models	Embedded		Sustainability and legacy.
			Operationalized		
			Institutionalized		

Table VII:6: Approach to data analysis using the good knowledge co-production principles (Norström, et al., 2020) and Tandem guide (Bharwani, et al., 2024).

Annex VII. Guidance for facilitators

Interactive exercises and materials for RWL stakeholder workshops

Facilitator Guidance Note

General guidance/ things to consider on workshop set up and facilitation

10. Facilitation guidance

- a. At the start of the meeting confirm group or meeting etiquette/ norms i.e. what are the 'rules of the room' and acceptable behaviour – e.g.
 - i. Listening to one another and not interrupting
 - ii. Allowing everyone to speak and contribute to discussions
 - iii. Support facilitators efforts to moderate
 - iv. Respect opinions
- b. Facilitation processes/ techniques
 - i. Ask open questions –How, When, What, Why, Where. Stimulate people to describe or explain rather than just Yes/No answers.
 - ii. Ask probing/ follow up TED Questions: **T**ell me, **E**xplain, **D**escribe and/ linking to demonstrate interest e.g. 'and then...'
 - iii. Request clarification, summarise and paraphrase to support active listening.
 - iv. Encouraging participation from those not speaking through 'whip arounds' – e.g. asking for quick comments from others
 - v. Allowing for some silence for group members to digest the question asked or after speaking to give space for them to continue to add e.g. 30 seconds
 - vi. Use 'parking lots' to capture questions/ input that is off topic and can be addressed outside the workshop.

See more details in Facilitators Handbook² (pg. 30 on group norms, pg. 77 on facilitation techniques)

- c. Competencies/ skills
 - i. Stay neutral, listen actively and honour all input from members.
 - ii. Maintain an objective, non-defensive, non-judgmental stance.
 - iii. Cultivate cultural awareness and sensitivity
 - iv. Be attuned to and reflect feelings
 - v. see more in the International Association of Facilitators (IAF) core competencies³.

² <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2020/The-Discussion-Group-Facilitators-Handbook.pdf>

³ <https://www.iaf-world.org/site/sites/default/files/Revised%20IAF%20Core%20%20Competencies%20-%20December%206%202021.pdf>

11. Setup of the room

- a. avoid rows of chairs and allow a round table set up
- b. Allow for wall space for sticking up paper
- c. Allow enough space to form a standing circle around the room

12. Materials

- a. name tags (either stickers or pre-printed)
 - b. Sticky notes (multiple colours)
 - c. Small stickers (helping to prioritise outputs from sticky notes)
 - d. Flip chart paper (for sticking on walls or using in the middle of round tables)
 - e. Maps of the area (hazards, vulnerability if possible)
 - f. Ball of string
 - g. Cup, rubber bands and string
 - h. Music - play some upbeat music during the breaks / interchanges
- Documentation
 - i. Ask people to sign in for documentation on who attended/ did not.
 - j. Approval for photography and recording/ notetaking/ data management in the workshop (later to have ethics approval added in agreements - tbc @max/ Paolo)
 - k. Dedicated note-takers at each station
 - i. Observe non verbal communication/ atmosphere and take notes
 - ii. Document 'why' there are different attitudes/ preferences among different stakeholders
 - l. Nominate a photographer to take pictures of 1) engagement in the room 2) of all outputs of the discussion (flipcharts, sticky notes etc.)
 - m. Store copies of the agenda, presentations, photos and notes in WP 1 NextCloud.

13. Evaluation

- a. End of workshop -evaluation questions (see suggestions at end of doc)
- b. Debrief between RWL facilitators WP 4/3/ on workshop challenges/ achievements
- c. Self-evaluation of facilitators
- d. Getting feedback/ reviewing outputs from workshop (e.g. stakeholder map)

Interactive activity suggestions

The following activities can be used to help engagement in the workshop. These are very flexible tools and can be adapted based on needs/ context.

Activity 1: Introduction ice-breaker ‘Bridging science-policy-practice’

Time requirement: 10 mins (near the beginning of the workshop or during the initial coffee/croissant - TBC).

Goal: Use this map later in the workshop to then fill in who is missing to meet the identified vision/ address the specified problem.

Preparation/ materials

- Identify three corners/ areas in the room and label them 1) Science 2) Policy/Planning 3) Practice with flip-chart paper stuck on the wall and sticky notes (all one colour).

Implementation steps

19. Ask everyone to write down their name/ organization and one word to describe why they are here on a sticky note. *Note: this could also be requested when they are signing in and can be in addition to their name tag (which they will keep with them).*
- Explain that there are three areas in the room and that Directed is aiming to connect different stakeholders and bridge science-policy-practice through the project.
- Ask everyone to stand up and move to the corner of the room where feel their role fits.
- Invite those who don't quite fit into one area to move somewhere in the room between them.
- The facilitator reflects on the distribution across the room e.g. we have a lot of rep from policy, let's learn more.
- The facilitator asks a selection of people (or everyone) to introduce themselves.
- The facilitator asks those in the middle or 'in-between' the others in particular to introduce themselves.
- The facilitator then moves two of the sheets close to the other sheet (so it is all in one area of the room) and sticks on the sticky notes from those in the middle of the room somewhere in between (or asks them to do).

Output: Mapping of the stakeholders present in the room.

Activity 2: Plenary/ World cafe - exercises

This activity includes three sub activities with at least one Directed facilitator per station.

- Problem analysis / priority mapping (2 parts)
- Stakeholder engagement
- Capacity and needs assessment

It will be implemented using

- World cafe - 3 stations and participants move after a set amount of time, the facilitator stays at their station and participants build on the output from the last group.
- Plenary – open discussion and quick Menti question

Time (approx.):

- 6 Plenary (setting the scene) 5-10 mins
- 7 Group work/ world cafe 45 mins (13 mins per table , 2 mins switching)
- 8 Plenary wrap up/ reflection (5 mins per table + 10 mins open discussion and Menti question)

Notes: 6-10 people per station. Depending on the number of participants. Allocate at least one facilitator per table (additional note taker if possible).

Feedback question: In the plenary feedback to ensure we captured all the ideas of the participants in the exercise.

- *What would the next years mean for you in Directed?* [open question/ 3 words]

• ***Problem analysis/ priority mapping***

This activity intends to support the RWLs in identifying issues and priorities (boundary conditions) regarding disaster and climate risks to premise and frame the delivery of further workshops. The intention is to provide practical solutions for identifying shared concerns across all involved stakeholders, and to establish a foundation for discussions regarding further stakeholder engagement for the RWLs to guarantee that they represent not only those with potential contributions to risk governance, but also to include those affected by decision making.

Time: 15 minutes | Before the first break

Implementation: Step 1 (Plenary)

- Ask everyone to write down (sticky notes) the most urgent priorities for disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation in _____ that DIRECTED can address?
- If you have a large map of the region available, ask participants to place these sticky notes on the map to identify most affected regions. Alternatively, use A4-sheets with name of the region written on them.

Implementation: Step 2 (World Cafe)

- Divide the participants into three groups

- Place the map with sticky notes on the table/floor and ask participants to identify priorities through the following exercise:
- Place the map/sheets of A4 with sticky notes on a flat surface.
- Provide each group (max. 8 people) with a paper cup inside a rubber band with strings attached to it. Make sure that all members have an end to hold to (Figure 1).
- Ask group members to coordinate and jointly move the cup onto the sticky notes which contains the highest risk/priority for action.

At the end of the exercise, jointly identify and discuss the four or five emerging risks/priorities and geographical areas of action through a plenary discussion.

Output

Shared understanding of the DRR and CCA priorities to be addressed in _____ under DIRECTED.

Note: Focus on documenting discussion with a focus on the *why* (reasons behind prioritisation of risk/challenge from different stakeholders). Take notes to enable analysis of the reasoning behind decision making.

2. Stakeholder engagement

Time: approx. 15 mins (per table)

Materials

- Flipchart paper or A3 printout (with table below).
- Markers

Steps:

The facilitator invites the group to reflect on the output from the ice-breaker exercise and think about the following questions. The answers from the questions can either be written by the facilitator directly on the table/paper or by individual members.

- **Who?** [linking to diversity/inclusion of actors]
 - Who are the key actors important to reach this vision/ address this challenge?
 - Who is missing from the room that needs to be part of the solution? e.g. civil society representation/ citizens, producers or users of data/models? Which of these should be involved in the co-production process?
 - Can we leverage/ engage champions or leaders?
 - Who is directly/ in-directly affected (either vulnerable to the challenge or able to take measures and influence decision making)?
- **Why?** [linking to power interest matrix/ relationships]
 - What is their role/ level of influence in decision-making/ policy?
 - How interested do we expect them to be?
 - What knowledge can they contribute? e.g. scientific model/data/ tools, local/ cultural
- **How to involve them?** [linking to activities in RWL]
 - Can/should we engage them as part of core RWL group and co-production process?

- Can we inform them with regular updates (e.g. briefing note, blogs, social media, ...) or other communication/outreach activities? or other?
- What methods of engagement/communication are needed to ensure differentiated groups (e.g. age, institution, gender, religion) are engaged? e.g. channelling through existing community networks.

Output: Visualisation / activity sheet for stakeholder mapping.

WHO?

WHY?

HOW?

.....

Additional information: 2-pager on stakeholder engagement guiding questions and excel template.

A follow up step can be to analyse the workshop data to update the excel template on stakeholder analysis and to draft a stakeholder map in Miro (that can be further validated by stakeholders).

3. Capacity and Needs Assessment

Time: 15 mins

Preparation/materials:

- Flipchart paper
- Markers
- Sticky notes

Steps:

- V. Within the small group ask participants to think for 1-2 mins about:
 - 5.3. Existing capacities within the region ____ to address the problem identified and build resilience
 - 5.3.1. models/data/tools
 - 5.3.2. communication systems
 - 5.3.3. coordination mechanisms/ partnerships
 - 5.4. Needs from Directed (i.e. gaps/ barriers that Directed can address)
 - 5.4.1. interoperability
 - 5.4.2. Access to models/data,
 - 5.4.3. improving coordination
 - 5.4.4. building networks
 - 5.4.5. knowledge exchange
- VI. Ask the participants to place these on the paper and position them on the page based on the strength of the capacity and the priority of the needs.
- VII. As the tables switch and new participants arrive, allow the new participants to reflect on those added and add additional capacities and needs – or add a ‘tick’ if

they support those already existing. New participants can also suggest moving the sticky notes up or down.

Output: Understanding of what capacities can be leveraged for the project and what are the biggest needs where Directed can contribute.

Note: If sticky notes are moved by other groups, monitor and note down key points from the discussion to enable analysis of the reasoning behind decision making.

Activity 3: Closing activity ‘Building our network’

Time: 10-15 mins before/ during the final wrap up

Goal: Invoke a sense of collaboration/ working-together within the RWL and ambition to connect/ strengthen networks with others not in the room.

Preparation/ materials:

- A ball of string
- Open space either around the tables or in an other room/ location
- Scissors

Steps:

- The facilitator asks the participants to form a circle in the room.
- The facilitator holds the ball of string and highlights that within Directed and the RWL we want to build a network across science, policy and practice.
- The facilitator highlights that as a fun way to do this, and to wrap up the meeting today, we’d like to ask each of you to share one ‘positive takeaway message’ from the meeting.
- The facilitator starts by sharing their own message and throws the ball of string to someone else in the room.
- This continues until everyone receives the ball of string.
- At the end the exercise the facilitator draws attention to the ‘network’ that can now be seen with the string - emphasizing that knowledge sharing and learning through this network will strengthen and we will extend the network (referring back to those that are not yet engaged).
- The string can then be cut to symbolise that now we need to return to our individual working routines but will continuously return to this collaborative network within the RWL.

Output: Smiling participants and picture of the network (nice moment for a group photo if feasible).

See more here: <https://guideinc.org/2015/11/11/team-building-activity-web-of-reflection/>

Additional 'Bonus' activity (optional) – Picture Puzzle

Time: 5 mins (possibly in-between presentations)

Preparation

- select a local picture related to 1) hazard (e.g. past event) 2) adaptation or DRR measure (e.g. flood wall, early warning system, nature based solution)
- Cut up the pictures into multiple puzzle pieces – making sure there is one piece per participant (e.g. cut in 2, 3 or 4 pieces).
- Put one piece on each chair.

Steps

- Invite all participants to take the puzzle piece on their chair and to move (or RUN) around the room.
- Give everyone 2-5 mins to find their matches and build the puzzle.
- Invite each group to reflect on the image and discuss the role they play in addressing this hazard or supporting this adaptation/ DRR solution.

Objective: help participants to get to know each other and understand their different roles.

Other resources:

Pearson, K.R., Backman, M., Grenni, S., Moriggi, A., Pisters, S., Vrieze de, A. (2018). Arts-Based Methods for Transformative Engagement: A Toolkit. Wageningen: SUSPLACE.

Available at: <https://edepot.wur.nl/441523>

<https://www.gamestorming.group/excursions>

<http://rapidgamesdesign.info/>

The use of serious games in engaging stakeholders for disaster risk reduction, management and climate change adaption information elicitation

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212420919307915#fig1>

Evaluation and Learning

Participant evaluation

The evaluation of the workshop can be conducted using different approaches:

- **Online survey tool** e.g. Google forms, Survey Monkey. This can be shared with participants via QR code (shown on PowerPoint) at the end of the workshop, asking participants to fill in during the last minutes of the workshop, with a reminder sent around to all participants after the workshop.
- **Paper forms.** These can be distributed at the end of the workshop to all participants and collected before they leave. The results will then need to be compiled into an excel file.
- **Online/interactive tool** e.g. Mentimeter, Slido. These tools offer the option to display the results of the evaluation questions in real-time with participants. Note that you may not want the participants to view the results, so you can decide to only show

some of the answers. Also note that some work ‘live’ so you need to actively move to the next question to collect responses so be aware that this may take more time than a regular survey online tool.

Time: 10 mins

Suggested questions:

- To what extent have the following developed through the workshop? [Scale 1-5 where 1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree]
 - Your knowledge and skills related to disaster resilience/ adaptation
 - Your willingness to collaborate/ engage with others
 - Your understanding of the co-production process
 - Your understanding of the benefits of the Directed project
 - Your comfort participating in activities
- How do you want to continue to engage as a RWL? Rank the following in order of importance.
 - In-person meetings/workshops
 - Webinars/ online engagement
 - Bilateral meetings/ one-to-one discussions
- How can we measure successful engagement in the RWL? Rank the following in order of importance.
 - Level of inclusion/diversity of participants
 - Strengthening of relationships/ networks
 - Access to new knowledge
 - Clear communication
 - Maintaining interest
 - Transparency about the process

5. Is there any other feedback or additional information you would like to share to inform engagement activities? [open question]

Other possible open questions:

- What did you find most useful about the workshop?
- What did you find difficult in the workshop?
- How could such workshops be improved in the future?

Facilitation debriefing and reflection

Debriefing meeting to be set up with WP 3/4 and RWL to reflect on the following:

Workshop attendance

- Were you happy with level of attendance vs. who was invited?
- Was it mentioned during the workshop that others should be included in the future?
- Was there a good gender balance and representation from different sectors?

Directed interest / problem identification

- Did the participants understand the objectives of Directed?
- How was Risk-Tandem presented?

- Did they ask for more information in breaks etc.? If so, what materials/ links were shared.
- Was there a clear understanding (consensus) at the end on the focus area/ key problems Directed can address?
- Did participants demonstrate interest in continuing engaging in RWL?

Interactive process

- Was there an interactive opening/introduction/ warm-up activity?
- How comfortable were the participants with the workshop and interactive format?
- What worked well / didn't work well?
- What aspects of the materials could we integrate next time?

Facilitation / participation

- How did you find the facilitation of the World Cafe groups?
- Did all participants speak/ have their voice heard?
- Can you explain more about any dominant voices? Such as those from stakeholders representing emergency response?
- Were there any tensions/ difficult interactions? If so, how did you manage this?

Networking/ relationship building

- Did you notice people talking to each other that usually would not?
- Did participants use the opportunity share information on their ongoing work that others could benefit from?

Partners

